

Predictive sensorimotor processing in the vertebrate brain

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Declaration

This thesis titled ‘Predictive sensorimotor processing in the vertebrate brain’, is a presentation of my original research work. Wherever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due reference to the literature, and acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions. The work was done under the guidance of Dr. Vatsala Thirumalai, at the National Centre for Biological Sciences, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bangalore.

Sriram Narayanan

In my capacity as supervisor of Sriram Narayanan’s thesis, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

Dr. Vatsala Thirumalai

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Acronyms

CF	climbing fiber
CSV	comma separated values
DAC	digital to analog converter
DAQ	data acquisition
DIFF	differential illumination focal filtering
dpf	days post fertilization
ETL	electrically tunable lens
FOV	field of view
fps	frames per second
FWHM	full width at half maximum
GaAsP	gallium arsenide phosphide
GC	granule cell
GUI	graphical user interface
I2C	inter-integrated circuit
IC	integrated circuit
IR	infrared
ISS	instantaneous swim strength
JSON	JavaScript object notation
LCD	liquid crystal display
LED	light emitting diode

LFM	light field microscopy
MS222	ethyl 3-aminobenzoate methanesulfonate
NA	numerical aperture
OKR	optokinetic response
OMR	optomotor response
OSC	open sound control
PC	Purkinje cell
PE	prediction error
PF	parallel fiber
PMT	photomultiplier tube
PSF	point spread function
ROI	region of interest
sCMOS	scientific complementary metal-oxide semiconductor
SNR	signal to noise ratio
TTL	Transistor-transistor logic

Chapter 1

Introduction

The ability of an organism to generate appropriate behavioral responses is critical for its survival. How the brain generates meaningful behavior in response to environmental and self-driven cues is a fundamental question that drives the field of systems neuroscience. Complexity in the brain can be found at multiple levels, ranging from sub-cellular processes to brain-wide networks working together to generate behavior (Sporns, 2022). A description of function across these levels is therefore an essential step towards understanding how the brain works. Over the past century, experimental and theoretical studies have made significant progress in deciphering the mechanisms underlying the organization and function of the brain. With advances in technology, it has become increasingly common to have access to brain activity measurements and manipulation at wider/finer scales than ever before. However, despite these advances, we are a long way away from understanding how distributed brain-wide networks of neurons give rise to meaningful and adaptable behavior. Taking inspiration from the framework proposed famously by David Marr and many others (Marr, 2010; Braitenberg, 1986; Tinbergen, 1963; Krakauer et al., 2017), this thesis attempts to describe behavior at an algorithmic level, keeping in mind the ethological significance to the animal and subsequently analysing brain function within this framework to describe how the brain might implement such an algorithm.

1.1 Learning to predict: mechanisms underlying complex behavior

An important feature of animal behavior across species is that it is highly adaptable and depends strongly on past experience. The brain has the remarkable ability to change how it responds in the same context, based on prior experience. These changes are not random and are guided by the outcome of a previous encounter. Feedback from the environment and an internally generated expectation are matched to generate an error signal, which serves to drive learning in the direction that minimizes the mismatch between the two (Keller and Mrsic-Flogel, 2018; Hertäg and Clopath, 2022; Schultz and Dickinson, 2000; Lindsay, 2021). This is an elegant way to

shape behavior to achieve arbitrary end goals. A similar error driven learning rule is used to train artificial neural networks (Rumelhart et al., 1986) and the subsequent discovery of prediction errors in the brain (Schultz, 2016; Schultz and Dickinson, 2000) led to the hypothesis that the brain learns by minimizing the difference between an internally generated prediction and ground truth sensory feedback. An error signal has been observed across a variety of contexts, ranging from reward prediction in the dopamine system (Schultz, 2016) to fast, online error computation by the cerebellum for motor control (Wolpert and Kawato, 1998). Recent experiments conducted on mice behaving in virtual reality where specific errors were introduced by the experimenter have revealed prediction errors even at the preliminary stages of sensory processing (Keller et al., 2012). This suggests that learning to predict is a ubiquitous and integral part of brain function (Keller and Mrsic-Flogel, 2018; Schultz and Dickinson, 2000).

Computing error signals is a difficult task and we do not yet understand the neural mechanisms involved (Keller and Mrsic-Flogel, 2018; Hertäg and Clopath, 2022). The consequences of an action are often only apparent after a significant delay. To compute error in these circumstances, the brain must compare signals that are separated by unpredictable lengths of time, which could be even seconds or more apart (Kim et al., 2020). How this computation is performed is an ongoing and intense topic of study in the field. Once an error has been detected, it must then be used to specifically adapt an internal model of the world to make better predictions next time. How error signals map onto appropriate target neurons/synapses and implement learning is not well known. The mechanisms of error driven learning may not be the same for all contexts and across different brain circuits. For example, motor control loops implemented by the cerebellar circuit likely utilize learning rules different from those involved in reward based reinforcement learning.

Once the brain is able to make predictions to guide behavior, it can be said that it has internalized the rules of the world and how to interact with it. The neural systems that enable the brain to do so are generally referred to as ‘internal models’. Internal models of motor control have been studied extensively. Motor control requires multiple control loops to be implemented by the brain acting across multiple timescales. Over immediate timescales, when a motor com-

mand is generated, a forward model is used to predict its real world consequence. This can be used to 1) correct for errors before the execution of the command, or 2) to cancel out self induced sensory feedback in order to be sensitive to changes in the external world. The motor command itself may be erroneous and the real world consequence of it may not be what was desired. In this scenario, sensory feedback is used by the motor system to deduce what command could have caused the error and updates to the command generation process is made such that future errors are minimized. The mechanisms involved in estimating the motor command from its sensory consequence are referred to as inverse models. Over longer timescales, the motor system puts together a sequence of movements to achieve a desired goal. It can be hypothesized that if the immediate consequences of a motor command can be predicted accurately, an internal model can be trained to put together more complex sequences or to plan what actions to perform over longer timescales. The cerebellum is a highly conserved vertebrate brain region shown to be involved these forms of model based control of movements. It is believed that parallel cerebellar circuits simultaneously implement these control loops to generate error free movements (Wolpert and Kawato, 1998).

Models of the environment are more abstract and context dependent. They can guide complex behavioral actions such as foraging and threat avoidance (Claudi et al., 2022; Rosenberg et al., 2021) over timescales beyond what is required for fine motor control. Dopamine dependent reinforcement learning is an example of a predictive mechanism operating over this timescale (Kim et al., 2020). Recently, it has been shown that the cerebellum is also involved in predictive functions in this domain (Wagner et al., 2017), suggesting that its circuit architecture with error feedback loops may be more generally applicable. Very little is known about how arbitrary expectations are internally generated and compared with real world outcomes to guide learning.

Since the brain interacts with the environment through the motor system, models of the external environment and the motor system itself are not independent of each other. It can be argued that a novel environment that is highly consistent would be easier for the motor system to adapt to than an environment that is inconsistent or unpredictable. When the environment

itself is unpredictable, relying strongly on individual experiences or 'trials' to adapt the motor program would be maladaptive. It is therefore important for the motor system to learn how fast to learn based on the model of the environment. Studies performed on human subjects suggests that this is indeed the case (Gonzalez Castro et al., 2014; Herzfeld et al., 2014). By introducing invisible force-fields in a reaching task, Gonzalez Castro et al. (2014), find that when the force-fields are repetitive and consistent, the motor adaptation rate is high and it is low when the force-fields are inconsistent. Their results suggest that rather than relying on immediate sensory feedback, the motor system sets its adaptation rate using a predictive model of the environment built with experience.

The idea that the brain internalizes the rules of the world was proposed well before the age of systems neuroscience (Craik, 1967; Keller and Mrsic-Flogel, 2018). Experiments to test this theory are complex and require brain activity measurements to be made in animals interacting with their environment in a meaningful way. Technological advances have enabled activity measurements from single neurons or populations of neurons in freely moving animals and in restrained animals behaving in virtual reality environments. The advantage of virtual reality is that the experimenter can control most aspects of the interaction between the animal and its world and intentionally introduce errors to probe for the neural mechanisms involved in detecting them (Keller et al., 2012; Ahrens et al., 2012). The experiments presented in this thesis have been performed with head-restrained larval zebrafish behaving in a virtual environment, while population activity in cerebellar neurons was imaged simultaneously.

1.2 Behavioral repertoire of larval zebrafish

Larval zebrafish offer many advantages as a model system to study behavior and brain function. From 4 days post fertilization (dpf), they become fully functioning independent individuals (Budick and O'Malley, 2000; Fero et al., 2011; Orger and de Polavieja, 2017; Portugues and Engert, 2009). They actively pursue and hunt prey, escape threats that are detected visually and through vibrations in the water and exhibit a range of homeostatic behaviors to position themselves within a favourable environmental niche (Patterson et al., 2013; Temizer et al., 2015; Haesemeyer et al., 2018; Petrucco et al., 2022; Lovett-Barron et al., 2020). At the same

time, their small size, genetic tractability and transparency allows brain activity recordings and manipulations to be performed non-invasively using imaging and optogenetic approaches (Ahrens et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2017; Lovett-Barron et al., 2020).

1.3 Recording brain activity at scale in behaving larval zebrafish

Various imaging methods have been used over the years to non-invasively record the activity of large populations of neurons in the larval zebrafish brain. The brain of a 7-dpf larval zebrafish measures $\sim 800 \times 400 \times 250 \mu\text{m}$ and consists of $\sim 100,000$ neurons (Ahrens et al., 2012). It is possible to capture the activity of nearly all of these neurons at the same time with genetically encoded fluorescent calcium indicators, especially GCaMP, with the help of light-sheet (Ahrens et al., 2013) or light-field microscopy (Andalman et al., 2019). These techniques however use visible light for excitation of GCaMP, which might interfere with the behavior of the fish. Two-photon laser scanning microscopy is also a common method for imaging population activity. The infrared excitation wavelength used for GCaMP excitation is invisible to the fish and does not interfere with behavior, especially in response to visual stimuli (Ahrens et al., 2012; Lovett-Barron et al., 2020). Two-photon microscopy also provides the best spatial resolution among the methods discussed, but at the cost of slow scan rates. The various imaging methods available and reasons to select one over the other have been reviewed in chapter 5. Two-photon microscopy was selected as the method of choice for all of the experiments presented in this thesis.

1.4 Optomotor response in larval zebrafish

Whole-field visual motion triggers an innate, position-stabilizing motor response in most animal species. The optomotor response (OMR) in fish is believed to help them maintain their position in flowing water (Neuhauss et al., 1999; Orger et al., 2000). In addition to whole-field visual motion, fish have been shown to exhibit rheotaxis to maintain position, even in darkness (Oteiza et al., 2017). On the other hand, visual cues alone, even when fish are head-restrained, elicit strong stabilizing responses, indicating that either modality can by itself initiate a stabilization response (Portugues et al., 2015). This aspect of the OMR has been exploited to study

the underlying sensorimotor transformations involved by simultaneous analysis of brain-wide activity during OMR in restrained fish (Kramer et al., 2019; Naumann et al., 2016). In zebrafish, robust OMR is observed from 4-dpf. However, retinal projections to the brain reach their final targets ~7-dpf and most experiments by others in the field and us have been performed once they are at this stage of development.

Due to their small size and tractability, it is possible to record brain activity at single neuron resolution, across the whole brain of 7-dpf larval zebrafish (Ahrens et al., 2012). Multiple studies over the past decade have taken advantage of this system to identify brain regions involved in the sensorimotor transformations taking place during OMR. It is now believed that pre-tectal arborization fields AF5 and AF6 are the primary visual processing centres in the larval zebrafish brain where optic flow is detected (Baier and Wullimann, 2021). Single cell tracing has revealed projections from these areas to hindbrain regions including the cerebellum, but the functional nature of these projections and how their activity is transformed to motor commands is not known (Kramer et al., 2019). Studies so far have primarily focused on identifying the brain regions involved and on formulating an algorithmic description of the average behavioral response. Several questions remain to be answered ranging from the neural basis of how optic flow is detected by pooling inputs from multiple independent motion detection units (Bahl and Engert, 2020) to how other modalities such as flow sensing integrate with the OMR.

The OMR in larval zebrafish is not a purely reflexive behavior. The latency with which the response is initiated varies widely within the same individual for the same stimulus strength and is in the seconds range (Portugues et al., 2015). In comparison, long latency visually evoked escape responses average in the low hundreds of milliseconds timescale. Moreover, when restrained fish are presented with OMR stimuli in open-loop, they ‘give up’ in a matter of seconds when repeated attempts to stabilize do not have a consequence to their perceived position (Mu et al., 2019). When in closed-loop, robust OMR can be elicited for hours, without habituation (Ahrens et al., 2012). Restrained fish in closed-loop performing the OMR have been shown to learn the gain of the setup and adapt motor output to achieve a desired outcome (Portugues and Engert, 2011). In these experiments, the strength of coupling between the fish’s

motor output and the resultant visual feedback from the virtual world, i.e. the closed-loop gain, was varied from high to low with respect to the natural gain of the fish. In response to changes in gain, fish adapted their motor output in a manner indicating that they were compensating for the gain, suggesting that they planned how much to move during a swim bout and what motor command to generate in order to achieve a particular displacement in position. These observations strongly indicate that swim responses are not only a function of the current state of position instability, but are planned to achieve a precise outcome in the world and depend heavily on prior experience.

1.5 Larval zebrafish acquire internal models of the motor system and the environment

Multiple experimental observations suggest that larval zebrafish use internal models to generate behavior. Most notable observations come from closed-loop gain adaptation experiments described in the previous section. When placed in a closed-loop optomotor environment with unrealistic gains, head-restrained fish adapt their motor output to achieve a desired outcome in the virtual world (Portugues and Engert, 2011). The fact that they compare the observed consequence of their movements with an expectation of how much they should have moved and adapt future movements to correct for errors means that they have an internal representation of how motor commands map to real world consequences. Since the OMR is an innate behavior, no training was required, indicating that these mechanisms are an important part of the fish's natural behavior. Evidence from whole-brain imaging and manipulation experiments show that motor adaptation depends on the dorsal raphe nucleus and the cerebellum (Kawashima et al., 2016; Ahrens et al., 2012; Markov et al., 2021).

Analysis of larval zebrafish hunting live prey indicate that they might predict the trajectory of moving prey before executing a capture swim (Bolton et al., 2019). This behavior may be learnt based on the properties of the prey available to them. Fish acclimatized to moving prey get better at hunting over time and exhibit higher capture rates compared to fish that have only seen stationary food (Oldfield et al., 2020). The ability to adapt hunting strategy based on prior experience is indicative of an adaptable model of the environment.

Studies have reported cerebellum dependent associative conditioning in fish (Harmon et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2020). Of particular relevance to this thesis is tail flick conditioning, where head-restrained larval zebrafish learnt to flick their tails to a particular side chosen randomly to stop an aversive heat stimulus. Fish learnt how to turn off the aversive stimulus within 10 trials. Analysis of whole-brain activity revealed that the neural dynamics in the cerebellum predicted both timing and outcome of a behavioral decision more than 10s before the tail movement was made (Lin et al., 2020). This suggests a role for the cerebellum in learning the task and planning appropriate motor actions.

Taken together, these observations indicate that larval zebrafish use internal models of both their motor system and the environment to make predictions to guide behavior. The prominent role identified for the cerebellum in these studies makes it an interesting candidate region to study the neural mechanisms involved.

1.6 Anatomy and function of the cerebellum

The cerebellum is an ancestral brain region found in all vertebrates with conserved cell types, circuit architecture and function (Bae et al., 2009; Bell et al., 2008; Kandel et al., 2000). The major input layer to the cerebellum is composed of a large number of granule cells (GCs), which are the most numerous cell type found in the brain. The GCs receive excitatory input from mossy fibers originating from brain stem and spinal nuclei in mammals and convey sensory information from the periphery and the cortex to the GCs. Each GC receives inputs from ~3-7 mossy fiber boutons and expansively recodes the information encoded in these inputs. GCs send excitatory projections to downstream Purkinje cells (PCs) via parallel fibers (PFs). Within the molecular layer of the cerebellum, the PFs intersect orthogonally oriented PC dendrites along their length, forming a large number of weak synaptic contacts. The output from a very large number of GCs converge onto each PC. PCs receive a second source of excitatory input from climbing fibers (CFs) originating from the inferior olive. In contrast to the convergent connections from GCs, each PC is innervated by a single CF via strong synaptic connections. The PCs themselves are GABAergic and inhibit their downstream targets, which are eurydendroid cells in fish or deep cerebellar nuclear cells in mammals. Many PCs connect to the same

downstream neuron with estimated convergence ratios of $\sim 40:1$ in mice (Person and Raman, 2012) and up to $5:1$ in larval zebrafish (Harmon et al., 2020). The cerebellum is composed of repeating units of the same microcircuit. It is believed that CF input triggered complex spikes, bursts or calcium spikes in PCs, act as a teaching signal to adaptively filter GC inputs that lead to error-free behavior (Albus, 1971; Marr, 1969; Dean et al., 2010). The filtering of GC inputs with error feedback has been shown to be mediated by synaptic depression of GC inputs that are co-active with CFs (Ito, 2000). A schematic of the cerebellar microcircuit is shown in Figure 1.1 (illustration by Vandana).

Figure 1.1: A schematic of the cerebellar microcircuit

1.6.1 Role of the cerebellum in motor control

Cerebellar function has been historically studied in the context of motor control. Cerebellar dysfunction causes deficits in motor control and coordination. Lesions to the cerebellum lead to delays in initiation of movements and those movements that are initiated are not smooth. Experimental and theoretical studies over the years have shown that the cerebellum implements parallel error feedback loops to learn how to move to achieve a desired end goal and ensure that those movements that are executed follow the planned trajectory (Dean et al., 2010; Wolpert and Kawato, 1998). Although it is accepted that the cerebellum learns these internal models of motor control, it is relatively unknown how error signals are computed and how the out-

put of the cerebellum contributes to the ongoing motor command as well as planning future movements. Part of the difficulty arises from the fact that cerebellar output does not directly control movements. Output from the cerebellum forms recurrent loops with the cortex and basal ganglia through the thalamus and inferences about the contributions to movements need to be made at the level of the larger network, both within the cerebellum and across multiple brain regions (Kandel et al., 2000; Bostan and Strick, 2018; Chabrol et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2014; Gao et al., 2018; Pidoux et al., 2018).

1.6.2 Non-motor functions of the cerebellum

Apart from motor control, the cerebellum has more recently been shown to be involved in cognitive tasks. It is now widely recognized in the field that the circuit architecture of the cerebellum supports general purpose learning, independent of motor control. The same set of rules and recurrent feedback loops that enable the cerebellum to learn internal models of motor control appear to be used to learn more general internal models of the world to expect events such as rewards over timescales beyond immediate motor control (Wagner et al., 2017). Since the cerebellum is an evolutionarily early vertebrate brain structure, the underlying mechanisms might provide general insight into how the brain learns to predict using error feedback loops.

1.7 Role of the cerebellum in the zebrafish optomotor response

Several studies have analysed brain-wide activity in larval zebrafish during OKR (optokinetic response) (Portugues et al., 2014) and open-loop (Kramer et al., 2019; Naumann et al., 2016) as well as closed-loop OMR (Ahrens et al., 2012; Kawashima et al., 2016). These studies typically use analytical techniques, most often multiple regression and clustering, to identify neurons and brain regions tuned to specific stimulus features and behavioral responses (Ahrens et al., 2012; Miri et al., 2010; Portugues et al., 2014). Robust OKR is triggered by whole-field rotational motion whereas translational motion triggers OMR. It is however likely that both rotational and translational motion would trigger both OKR and OMR, but this has not been systematically investigated in the field. The OKR, like the OMR is not a purely reflexive behavior and is driven by a distributed set of visuo-motor centers (Portugues et al., 2014). How

the brain makes a decision to stabilize gaze over position and the interaction between brain regions involved would be interesting to investigate.

The cerebellum has been shown to be active during both OMR and OKR. Both Purkinje and granule cells in the cerebellum show strong activation in response to optic flow stimuli and anatomical tracing has revealed direct projections from the pretectal regions involved in optic flow processing to the cerebellum (Kramer et al., 2019). The cerebellum is however not necessary for OMR. When either the inferior olive or the cerebellum was lesioned, nearly identical OMR was seen compared to non-lesioned fish. The lesioned fish however showed specific deficits in motor adaptation (Ahrens et al., 2012) or an expectation dependent component involved in the OMR as shown in this thesis.

1.8 Overview of this thesis

Experience changes how we perceive the world and interact with it. As animals interact with their environment, they learn to predict the consequences of their actions and to expect events such as rewards or threats. This understanding of how the world works allows the brain to generate optimal behavioral responses, beyond what is possible by reacting to sensory inputs alone. The ability of the brain to learn models of the world is widespread across the animal kingdom and can be broadly categorized into two groups. 1) Models of the motor system and the outcomes of motor commands. 2) Environmental models, which encode how the external environment behaves. The work presented in this thesis aims to understand the neural mechanisms that enable the brain to acquire internal models of both these forms in ethologically relevant regimes.

The cerebellum is a highly conserved vertebrate brain region shown to be involved in model based control of behavior. The circuit architecture of the cerebellum is nearly identical in larval zebrafish as other vertebrates, including humans. This thesis exploits the small size and accessibility of the larval zebrafish system to perform a circuit-wide analysis of cerebellar function while head-restrained fish behaved in a virtual reality environment. The properties of the virtual world and the coupling between the fish's tail movements and their consequences were

controlled/perturbed in our experiments to test how they learnt behaviorally relevant internal models of the world and how to interact with it.

The methods chapter in this thesis describes custom made experimental setups used to perform all of the experiments presented subsequently. This includes the design of an optomotor virtual reality environment for head-restrained larval zebrafish. The virtual environment coupled with a custom made two-photon microscope have been used extensively throughout this thesis for simultaneously imaging calcium activity in genetically identified cerebellar cell populations in behaving fish.

The first set of experiments were performed to study how fish adaptively regulate motor output to achieve a desired outcome in the virtual world. In these experiments, the sensitivity of coupling (gain) between tail movements of the fish and the resultant displacement in the virtual world was varied systematically. We find that fish learn to adapt to the new gain by instantaneous compensation of ongoing movements and by creating a stable, longer term understanding of the gain, built up over multiple swim events. Preliminary analysis of simultaneously recorded Purkinje cell population activity and a role for the cerebellum in motor adaptation are discussed.

In the following chapter, we probed whether fish could learn to expect repetitive behaviorally relevant optic flow stimuli in the virtual world. By introducing deviant stimuli with varying probability, we were able to determine that fish learnt to expect optic flow direction by integrating probability of occurrence over minute-timescales. Analysis of population activity revealed a fast acting, error feedback based mechanism implemented by the cerebellar circuitry which allowed fish to expect future stimuli and respond with lower latency.

The last chapter describes the design and construction of a digitally scanned light-sheet microscope to image calcium activity at cellular resolution, across the whole brain of a larval zebrafish. Preliminary recordings have been presented as a proof of concept. This setup can be used for whole-brain calcium imaging or fast, small field of view imaging of voltage sensors in behaving fish.

1.9 Publications arising from this thesis

1. Narayanan, S., Thirumalai, V., 2019. Contributions of the cerebellum for predictive and instructional control of movement. *Current Opinion in Physiology, Motor Control Systems* 8, 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cophys.2019.01.011>
2. Narayanan, S., Varma, A., Thirumalai, V., 2022. Rapid acquisition of internal models of stimulus patterns by Purkinje cells enables faster behavioral responses. *BioRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.04.28.441782>

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Chapter 2

Methods

This chapter describes most of the experimental protocols, setups and analysis methods used subsequently in chapters 3 and 4. When required, additional detail on methods used are included in individual chapters.

2.1 Fish

We used 6-8dpf zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) larvae for all experiments. Fish were raised in E3 medium (composition in mM: 5 NaCl, 0.17 KCl, 0.33 CaCl₂, 0.33 MgSO₄, 0.5 methylene blue) or fish facility water with 0.5mM methylene blue, at 28.5°C in accordance with standard protocols (<https://zebrafish.org/home/guide.php>). Tg(*aldoca:GCaMP6s*) ; *nacre*^{-/-} larvae (from Prof. Masahiko Hibi, Nagoya University, Japan) and Tg(*neurod:GCaMP6f*) ; *nacre*^{-/-} larvae (from Prof. Claire Wyart, I.C.M., Paris) (Rupprecht et al., 2016), outcrossed into the Indian wildtype (from local aquarium suppliers) background were used for experiments involving two-photon imaging. Indian wildtype larvae were used for electrophysiological recordings. Experiments were spread out over at least 3 different batches of larvae. All experimental procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of the National Centre for Biological Sciences.

2.2 Head-restrained experimental preparation

6-8 days post fertilization larval zebrafish were anaesthetized by briefly immersing them in 0.017% MS222 (Sigma-Aldrich) and embedded dorsal side up in a drop of 2% low gelling temperature agarose (Sigma-Aldrich) which was placed in the center of a 60mm petri dish lid. The orientation of the fish was adjusted before the agarose solidified using a size zero paintbrush which was trimmed down to 2-3 bristles. Once the agarose solidified, the dish was filled with E3 medium and the tail below the level of the swim bladder was freed using a scalpel

under a dissection microscope. The embedded fish were allowed to acclimatize for 4-8 hours before experiments were carried out.

The following steps helped maximize the success rate of the head-restrained experimental preparation: 1) Minimize duration of exposure to MS222. 2) Allow molten agarose to cool down to barely above gelling temperature before placing fish in it. 3) Wash off MS222 and excess water by first moving the fish around in an intermediate dish containing molten low gelling temperature agarose. 4) Take care not to injure skin while positioning the fish in molten agarose. 5) Acclimatize for a minimum of 3-4 hours before the experiment, with the last hour of acclimatization in the final position on the stage of the experimental setup. 6) Maintain temperature above $\sim 22^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the acclimatization period and during experiments. $>80\%$ of all head-restrained fish showed robust swim responses to optic flow.

2.3 Closed-loop virtual environment for larval zebrafish

Fish exhibit an innate behavioral response where they orient themselves against the direction of flowing water and compensate for involuntary drifts in position by generating forward swims of appropriate strength. This behavior can be recapitulated using optic flow stimulus alone and is referred to as the optomotor response (Neuhauss et al., 1999; Orger et al., 2000). Head-restrained fish show very low levels of spontaneous swimming and optic flow stimulus was provided to evoke swim responses. Tail movements in head-restrained fish during bouts of swimming, or extracellular motor recordings from paralyzed fish, were transformed in real-time to realistic swim velocity in a virtual world (Portugues and Engert, 2011; Ahrens et al., 2012). This setup allowed simultaneous neural recordings to be made while stationary, head-restrained fish swam forward in a virtual environment on a screen placed beneath them. Most experiments in this thesis have been performed using this custom designed experimental setup.

2.3.1 Visual stimulus

Software written in Processing 2.2.1 (<https://processing.org/>) was used to control the experimental protocol as well as to generate and update the visual stimulus at 120Hz. The

visual stimulus consisted of square wave grating with a spatial period of 10mm presented 5mm beneath the fish. During optic flow-on phases, the grating drifted at 10mm/s in the tail to head direction. Motor output of the fish during the optic flow-on phases resulted in realistic deceleration and a smooth change in direction of optic flow based on the following equation.

$$v_{grating_n} = v_{flow_n} - v_{swim_n}$$

Where $v_{grating_n}$, v_{flow_n} and v_{swim_n} are the instantaneous velocities at frame n of the grating stimulus, externally imposed optic flow and the velocity of the head-restrained fish in the virtual environment respectively. The estimation of realistic swim velocity based on motor output is described in the subsequent section.

Figure 2.1: Closed-loop optomotor setup for head-restrained fish

L1: f40mm moulded aspheric collection lens for collimating the 617nm LED; L2, L3: f120mm acrylic fresnel lenses sandwiching the LCD panel on either side, mounted using a 3D printed frame; F1: 675nm longpass filter; L4: f75mm projection lens to form an image of the LCD screen beneath the fish on the diffusive screen; L5: reversed Nikon 50mm f/1.8D lens with 24mm extension tube for fish tail imaging; F2a,b: 780nm bandpass filters for IR tail illumination and imaging. Figure 2.2 shows an annotated photograph of this setup.

Figure 2.2: Photograph of the closed-loop optomotor setup for head-restrained fish

In the calcium imaging setup, visual stimulus was projected on a 60mm diameter diffusive paper screen placed 5mm below the fish (Figure 2.1). The projector was custom built around a 5-inch LCD panel (Adafruit, with tfp401a HDMI decoder) removed from its housing. The LCD was illuminated from behind with a collimated 617nm LED (Luxeonstar) and was imaged onto the projection screen. The final pixel size on the projection screen was 0.32mm. A 5X5mm window was cut out in the projection screen to facilitate video recording of tail movements from below. A longpass filter (575lp, Chroma) was placed in the projection light path to prevent harmful levels of light from reaching the PMT. Figure 2.2 shows an annotated photograph of this setup. Visual stimulus for the electrophysiology experiments was presented directly on an LCD screen positioned beneath the fish.

2.3.2 Real-time motor output detection for closed-loop optomotor feedback

Custom Bonsai workflows (Lopes et al., 2015) were used for real-time motion detection. The algorithm used by our software for online motion detection closely matched previously published protocols (Ahrens et al., 2012; Portugues and Engert, 2011). Video based motion detection was done at 200fps using a Flea3-USB3.0 camera (FLIR) (Figure 2.1). The tail of the fish was illuminated from one side by a collimated 780nm LED (M780D2, Thorlabs) and imaged onto the camera sensor below, using a reversed Nikon 50mm f/1.8d lens with a 24mm extension tube for increased magnification. Both the illumination and imaging light paths were filtered through 780nm bandpass filters (FBH-780-10, Thorlabs). The imaging light path was filtered to exclude light from the visual stimulus and two-photon laser and the illumination light path was filtered to block low intensity visible light emission from the 780nm LED. Real-time motion detection was performed by frame subtraction. The fraction of motion pixels in each frame, which scales with the amount of tail movement, was lowpass filtered with a 10ms time constant to obtain the instantaneous swim strength (ISS). This lowpass filter simulates the inertial effects experienced by larval fish in water. The ISS was streamed in real-time using open sound control (OSC) protocol to custom software written in Processing 2.2.1. This software generated visual stimulus, executed the experimental protocol, and generated TTL signals to synchronize two-photon imaging or electrophysiology data acquisition.

ISS for the electrophysiology preparation was estimated from fictive swims recorded unilaterally from the ventral root (Figure 2.3). Analog output from the recording amplifier was digitized at 12kHz in 10ms chunks using a DAQ card (PCIe-6361, National Instruments) and acquired in a Bonsai workflow. Each 10ms chunk was bandpass filtered between 0.2-5kHz. The standard deviation of each chunk was calculated and the offset induced by recording noise was subtracted. This signal was lowpass filtered at 10Hz and thresholded manually to obtain an estimate of the ISS, which was streamed to the experiment control software.

Figure 2.3: Closed-loop optomotor setup for paralyzed fish

The ISS was scaled individually for each fish to obtain a realistic estimate of swim velocity. 1-3 trials of optic flow at 10mm/s lasting 10-15s were presented before the start of each experiment, in the open-loop configuration. A scaling factor, s , was calculated from these trials such that the ISS when scaled resulted in an average swim bout velocity of 12mm/s. This process is described by the following equation.

$$v_{swim_n} = s \times g \times ISS_n$$

Where n is the frame count. v_{swim} is the instantaneous velocity of the fish in the closed-loop environment. s is the scaling factor set individually for each fish. g is the gain of the closed-loop feedback, where a gain of 1.0 corresponds to the realistic coupling between the strength of tail movement and swim velocity. A lower or higher gain setting compared to the native gain of 1.0 leads to proportionately lower or higher swim velocities respectively.

2.3.3 Measurement of lag in closed-loop feedback

Delay in closed-loop feedback is largely due to the 60Hz refresh rate and frame buffering in the control hardware of the LCD screen. These delays cannot be quantified accurately in software and were measured independently using a high-speed camera at 250fps. The time taken for pixel intensity to change on the screen in response to a trigger signal was quantified. An LED in the FOV of the high-speed camera delivered a trigger flash, which was analysed in real-time using the closed-loop software (Figure 2.4A). Pixels on the LCD screen was set to white when

the LED was detected to be on (Figure 2.4B) and black when the LED was detected to be off (Figure 2.4C). The LCD screen was placed in the FOV of the high-speed camera along with the triggering LED so that the delay between the trigger event and its effect on the screen could be quantified. Using this method, the latency of closed-loop feedback was found to be 47-54ms (Figure 2.4D). This measurement represents the overall lag from video acquisition to visual stimulus update.

Figure 2.4: Measurement of lag in closed-loop feedback

(A) Schematic of the setup used to measure latency of the closed-loop system. (B,C) LCD pixel responses to trigger LED on (B) and off (C). Traces are normalized to max intensity and triggered to the onset ($t=0s$) of change of LED state. (D) Response latency of the LCD screen to the on and off transitions of the trigger LED.

2.3.4 2D virtual environment

A 2D virtual environment was created for head-restrained fish by performing real-time video based motion detection independently for left and right tail beats to determine turn angles based on relative difference in between left and right sides. The angle component was added to the forward velocity component for each swim bout and an egocentric rotation and translation of the visual scene was performed according to tail beat asymmetry and vigor respectively. This setup was made as proof of concept and can be used for the study of complex behaviors such as phototaxis, which would benefit from the use of 2D virtual environments.

2.3.5 Modular organization of closed-loop software

The different functional blocks of the closed-loop software have been designed such that the various motion detection methods can be selected independent of the rest of the workflow and

vice versa. This allows for a seamless transition between video based 1D, video based 2D or electrophysiology based 1D motion detection methods, while selecting the appropriate virtual arena to couple to. Users can configure and run experiments without explicit knowledge of programming. Compatibility of various motion detection methods and virtual environments are shown in Table 2.1.

Motion detection	OSC protocol	Virtual environment
Video based 1D	common	1D arena (infinite dimensions)
Video based 2D		2D arena (finite dimensions)
Fictive swim based 1D		1D arena (infinite dimensions)

Table 2.1: Compatibility of modular elements of the closed-loop software

2.3.6 Programming protocols for closed-loop experiments and simultaneous two-photon imaging

The experimental protocol is defined in a human readable JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) file, which is generated automatically using a python script. With this script, the user defines a behavior experiment consisting of single or multiple trials of stimulus presentation. Each trial is defined as a sequence of one or more segments of optic flow stimulus with a duration, flow velocity and closed-loop gain. Trials can be repeats of the same or different from each other. By default, a TTL pulse is generated at the start of each trial to synchronize microscope acquisition.

In addition to the JSON protocol file, this python script also generates a ScanImage 3.8 (see section 2.5.1) compatible cycle file for automatically sequenced microscope acquisition. The cycle file is generated programmatically from the JSON protocol file. The cycle file encodes the number of segments of imaging, their duration and optionally other parameters like x-y-z position and ROI properties. This allows serial, automated random access imaging of any region of interest in the larval fish brain. Calcium imaging can be carried out in multiple

arbitrarily long segments within the behavior protocol. The total imaging time is therefore equal to or less than the duration of the behavior protocol defined in the JSON file. Typically, each segment of microscope acquisition is started at the beginning of each trial by the TTL pulse generated by an arduino connected to the behavior computer (see below). An inter trial interval (ITI) if any, where no imaging is carried out, is added to the end of each trial by setting a shorter duration for microscope acquisition. The ScanImage cycle file is formatted with line feed and carriage return characters usually hidden by text editors. Care must be taken while editing manually.

To begin an experiment, the JSON file is loaded onto the closed-loop experiment control software and the corresponding cycle file is loaded onto the microscope control software (Scan-Image). Acquisition is initiated once and both the behavior and imaging protocols are carried out to completion automatically. The experiment control software saves a copy of the JSON file along with the acquired behavior data for future reference and analysis.

2.4 Behavior assays

2.4.1 Gain adaptation experiments

The gain of the closed-loop feedback was varied between 1.0, 0.5 and 2.0 in these experiments. The specific protocols used in terms of timing of trials and inter-trial interval is mentioned along with the results. A gain of 0.5 or 2.0 results in half or double the expected closed-loop swim velocity as expected by the fish respectively. These experiments were performed to analyse how fish adapt their motor output to compensate for changes in gain, which would indicate that they have an expectation of how their body displaces given a motor command.

2.4.2 Bout-clamp experiments

Optic flow induces a robust optomotor response in head-restrained fish where they generate swim bouts regularly at ~ 1 Hz. The slow kinetics of the GCaMP6s calcium sensor, which has a decay timecourse of 1.7s makes it difficult to correlate swim bout kinematics of individual bouts with calcium responses in Purkinje cells as calcium signals due to multiple swim bouts

sum together. To isolate Purkinje cell calcium responses to individual swim bouts, a ‘bout-clamp’ protocol was set up in which the optic flow was set to zero as soon as the first swim bout was complete. This allowed many isolated swim bouts and corresponding Purkinje cell calcium responses to be captured and analysed. Experiments were performed with this protocol where the flow velocity was varied to induce single swim bouts of varying strengths, while Purkinje cell calcium activity was imaged simultaneously. The acquired data is available for future analysis.

Figure 2.5: Bout-clamp protocol to elicit spaced out individual swim bouts

2.4.3 Experiments to test stimulus expectation

In this assay, head-restrained larval zebrafish were presented with repetitive 2s long pulses of optic flow stimulus separated by 5s of no optic flow. During the optic flow-on period, the gain of the closed loop feedback was set to 1.0 to provide realistic visual feedback during swim bouts in order to maintain consistent levels of behavioral responsiveness (Portugues and Engert, 2011; Mu et al., 2019). Deviant optic flow stimuli (‘probe’ stimuli) were introduced at low probability to look for behavioral and neural signatures indicating that the fish learnt to expect a previously experienced stimulus based on the probability of its occurrence. Further details on specific stimuli and protocols used are described in chapter 4.

2.4.4 Estimation of latency modulation

Latency modulation around the probe stimulus was estimated by determining the fold change in response latency relative to baseline latency (Figure 4.7A,B). The baseline was determined as the mean latency observed across 5 pulses of 1cm/s forward optic flow before the probe pulse. This normalization was necessary as slow drifts in latency developed over the duration of the experiment. Traces were selected if there were at least 3 swim bouts on either side of the probe stimulus within a window of 5 forward optic flow stimuli. A minimum of 3 such traces were required per fish to obtain an average latency modulation trace for that fish. These criteria were pre-selected before the analysis was performed and the statistical inference did not change when we later varied the selection criteria to include probe stimuli with at least 1 swim bout on either side. 17 out of 27 non-lesioned fish (Figure 4.7C) and 11 out of 11 cerebellum lesioned fish (Figure 4.7D) passed these exclusion criteria.

2.4.5 Circular optomotor track for free-swimming fish

Head-restrained larval zebrafish rarely swim spontaneously, whereas unrestrained fish swim constantly in discrete bouts at a baseline rate of ~ 1 Hz. A circular optomotor track was set up for freely moving fish in order to recreate an infinite optomotor track similar to the 1D closed-loop environment for the restrained fish (Figure 2.6A). In this setup, fish were placed in a 15mm wide circular channel of water with outward sloping walls at a 10° angle made from molecular biology grade agarose. The channel was made by casting molten agarose around a 3D printed mould. Beneath this dish, a radial grating pattern which rotated around the center of the dish was presented on an LCD screen (Figure 2.6A,B). Fish were illuminated from below using an 840nm high power LED and high speed videos were captured at 150Hz by a Flea3-USB3.0 camera (FLIR) with a Nikon 50mm f1.8D lens using a custom bonsai workflow. Visual stimulus was excluded from the captured video using a 715nm longpass colored glass filter (Thorlabs). The coordinates of the centroid of the fish were extracted online in the same bonsai workflow as the video was being recorded (Figure 2.6C). Stimulus presentation and video capture were synchronized by TTL pulses generated by the stimulus presentation software, written in Processing 2.2.1, at the beginning and end of the protocol. Robust optomotor

response was observed and fish were videotaped continuously for 1 hour.

Figure 2.6: Circular optomotor track for free swimming fish

(A) Schematic of the experimental setup. (B) Radial grating stimulus presented beneath the fish. The angle of the wedges are chosen to obtain a spatial period of 10mm across the center of the 15mm channel of water. (C) Snapshot of an experiment showing a fish with real-time tracking overlaid for the past 200 frames. Coordinates are color coded with the green end of the scale representing the most recent frame. The central obstruction is 15mm in diameter on the top surface. Both the outside walls and the central obstruction had sloping walls at a 10° angle.

2.5 Custom two-photon microscope

2.5.1 Optical layout

Two-photon calcium imaging was performed on a custom made microscope (Figures 2.7 and 2.8) controlled using ScanImage 3.8 (Pologruto et al., 2003). A Ti-Sapphire laser (Chameleon Ultra II, Coherent) tuned to 920nm was used to excite GCaMP (Chen et al., 2013) using a laser power of 10-30mW (depending on the experiment) at the sample plane. The laser was focused at the sample plane using a 20× 1.0NA objective lens (XLUMPLFLN20XW, Olympus), downstream of 50mm and 300mm focal length achromatic scan and tube lenses (AC-300-050B and AC-508-300-B, Thorlabs). Scanning was achieved using 3mm aperture galvanometer scan mirrors (6215H, Cambridge Technology). Fluorescence emission from GCaMP was reflected orthogonally away from the excitation path by a large, 50mm diameter dichroic (FF605-Di02-50-D, Semrock) placed close to the back aperture of the objective lens. The reflected emission was collected with a 50mm diameter, 40mm focal length aspheric lens (AL5040-A, Thorlabs), filtered through a green emission filter (FF01-520/70, Semrock) and detected with a high sensitivity GaAsP PMT (H7422PA-40, Hamamatsu).

Laser intensity was controlled using a rotatable half-wave plate (HWP) upstream of a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) cube (refer to Malus's law). The intensity controlled beam was expanded to a diameter of 3mm with the help of a Galilean telescope and directed into the scan path of the microscope using plane mirrors. The scan and tube lenses have a magnification ratio of 6× (ratio of focal lengths) and expand the 3mm input beam to 18mm, which is equal to the back aperture of the objective lens, thereby fully utilizing the NA of the objective lens for excitation. Even though the excitation light used is monochromatic, achromatic scan and tube lenses minimize spherical aberration and coma, resulting in a tighter point spread function, thereby increasing two-photon excitation efficiency. The optical configuration described above resulted in a point spread function with a full width at half maximal intensity of 640×640×1370nm (x, y, z) and allowed continuous imaging for multiple sessions, each tens of minutes long, with minimal photobleaching.

Figure 2.7: Optical layout of the custom two-photon microscope

Figure 2.8: Photograph of the custom two-photon microscope

2.5.2 Functional layout

The microscope was controlled by the open source ScanImage 3.8 software (Figure 2.10). Scanning and data acquisition from the PMT was controlled by the same DAQ card (PCI-6110, National Instruments, NI-DAQ 1). Current output from the PMT, proportional to the intensity of detected light, was amplified and converted to a voltage signal using a transimpedance amplifier (SR570, Stanford Research Systems) with a gain of 200nA/V. The resultant voltage signal was acquired and binned into pixels with a dynamic range of 12 bits. Data acquisition from the microscope was triggered by a TTL pulse generated by an arduino connected to a separate computer running the behavior protocol (Figure 2.11).

Peripheral devices, namely the intensity control mechanism and the laser shutter, were controlled by a second DAQ card (PCI-6223, National Instruments, NI-DAQ 2). Intensity control

was achieved by coupling the rotation of a servo motor (S2003, Futaba) to the rotational mount of the half-wave plate using plastic gears (Figure 2.12). The shutter was custom made using a salvaged laptop hard-drive, whose read-head was actuated to physically block or unblock the laser beam (Figure 2.13). In the 'external trigger mode', ScanImage exhibited non-ideal behavior by pre-emptively opening the shutter in anticipation of a trigger signal to start acquisition. This was problematic as a stationary beam rapidly lesions tissue. A custom driver board was designed which opened the shutter only when scanning began while in the external trigger mode. This was achieved by performing logical operations on the ScanImage shutter state signal, the external trigger signal, and a trigger mode signal (externally triggered or not), on an Attiny85 microcontroller, which then actuated the shutter only when scanning was taking place (Figure 2.14).

Figure 2.9: Functional layout of the two-photon microscope and synchronization with the behavior experiment software

The microscope is programmed to acquire a pre-determined sequence of frames when triggered externally by an arduino connected to the behavior software running on a separate computer. The behavior software acquires high-speed videos of the fish tail, generates the visual stimulus and executes the experimental protocol.

Figure 2.10: ScanImage 3.8 software with custom GUIs for laser power and shutter control

Figure 2.11: Schematic and photograph of the arduino triggering circuit to synchronize calcium imaging acquisition with the behavior experiments

Parts: Arduino UNO, BC547 NPN transistors, R1-9: 10kΩ resistors, D1,D2: 1N4148 diodes.

Figure 2.12: Laser intensity control

(A) Optoisolator circuit to isolate the NI-DAQ card from external circuitry. Parts: 4N25 or equivalent optocoupler, R1,2: 1k Ω and 10k Ω resistors. (B) Photograph of the servo motor coupled to the rotational mount with the half-wave plate.

A

Figure 2.13: Photograph of the custom made laser shutter

Hard disk read head modified to function as a millisecond timescale laser shutter in the closed (A) and open (B) configurations. The shutter driver circuit can be seen mounted on top of the shutter. Beam path is highlighted in yellow. The polarizing beam splitter cube can be seen, although not in focus, in the foreground.

Figure 2.14: Schematic of the shutter driver circuit

Parts: Attiny85 microcontroller, 7809 and 7805 voltage regulators, 4N25 optocoupler, C1-4: 0.22 μ F capacitors, R1-3,5,8: 10k Ω resistors, R4,6: 1k Ω resistors, R7: 10-20 Ω 2W resistor to limit current draw and consequently the speed of the shutter. Lower values can be used but will lead to the generation of excess heat. D1-4: 1N4007 diodes.

2.5.3 Eliminating visual stimulus contamination

The 575nm longpass filter in the visual stimulus projection path, in combination with the green emission filter, blocked most but not all visual stimulus light from reaching the PMT. Noise from visual stimulus bleedthrough due to imperfect optical filtering was sufficient to cause significant degradation of GCaMP signal quality, since photon rates from fluorescence emission are low. To eliminate contamination from visual stimulus, a custom made driver (Figures 2.15, 2.16) was used to power the projector LED antiphase to the line scans of the fast x-galvo during two-photon imaging. This removed any possibility of bleedthrough of visual stimulus light into the calcium imaging channel. The strobing of visual stimulus happens in the kHz frequency range and is imperceptible to fish as it is well beyond the ~30Hz flicker fusion frequency of their visual system (Seeliger et al., 2002).

Bidirectional scanning was used in all experiments in Chapter 4. At either end of each scan line, the visual stimulus LED was turned on during the turnaround phase and was turned off during the acquisition phase (Figure 2.17A). The turnaround phase was 18% of the total scan time for each line. While not scanning, the stimulus projection was constantly on and LED brightness was reduced to match the average brightness while being strobed during scanning. This was achieved using two independently triggered voltage controlled current sources turned on or off by an Attiny85 microcontroller which received the line clock from the two-photon microscope as input (Figure 2.15). At any given instance, one of the current sources was triggered on and the other one was set to be off. The output current of each of the current sources was set independently using a potentiometer. One of them was used to strobe the stimulus antiphase with scanning, hence was set to power the LED brighter when it was on. The other one was used to continuously power the LED at a lower intensity when not scanning. Average stimulus intensities were matched during both phases by manual calibration using a light meter.

Figure 2.15: Schematic of the line clock synchronized LED driver circuit

Parts: Attiny85 microcontroller, 7809 and 7805 voltage regulators, 4N25 optocoupler, LM324 opamp, C1-4: 0.22μF capacitors, BS170 mosfet, IRF540 power mosfet, D1-2: 1N4148 diodes, RV1,RV2: 1kΩ trimmer potentiometers, R1: 11kΩ, R2,3,5,7: 10kΩ, R4,6: 2.2kΩ, R8,9,10,12: 820Ω, R11,13: 2.2Ω 2W resistors.

Figure 2.16: Photograph of the line clock synchronized visual stimulus LED driver circuit

Figure 2.17: Response characteristics of the line clock synchronized visual stimulus LED driver

(A) Bidirectional scan pattern for a single frame of two-photon acquisition. The turnaround phase and acquisition phase are highlighted. Visual stimulus projector LED is turned on only in the turnaround phase, thereby eliminating contamination in the GCaMP signal. (B) Validation of the synchronized stimulus driver. The line clock signal (red) is programmed to be high during the acquisition phase and low during the turnaround phase. The output of the line clock signal was phase shifted from the true line clock by adding a 600 μ s delay in to the clock output of the NI card. This allowed a ‘virtual’ turnaround phase to be captured by the PMT as an image was acquired. The visual stimulus bleedthrough to the PMT during the ‘virtual’ turnaround phase is time-locked with microsecond precision to the clock signal.

2.6 Sample alignment protocol

The closed-loop optomotor setup was mounted on a motorized X-Y stage (XYR-4040, Dover motion) and placed beneath the objective of the two-photon microscope (Figure 2.2). Fish were mounted within the FOV of the closed-loop camera with the help of alignment marks placed on a transparent dish with a fine scalpel under a dissection microscope. A sheet of paper with boundaries printed on it using a desktop printer was placed beneath the dish to guide the placement of the alignment marks. Once mounted, the fish, along with the rest of the closed-loop setup could be moved together using the motorized X-Y stage and brought into the FOV of the two-photon microscope.

2.7 Purkinje cell calcium imaging

Head-restrained Tg(*aldoca:GCaMP6s*) ; *nacre*^{-/-} larvae were used to image Purkinje cell calcium activity. A single 512×128 pixel field of view with 0.53μm pixel size, centered around the Purkinje cell layer was scanned using a pixel dwell time of either 1.6μs (Figure 4.6) or 3.2μs (all other experiments), resulting in frame rates of either 7.8Hz or 3.9Hz respectively. Laser power measured at the sample plane was 10-15mW for 3.2μs pixel dwell time and 20-30mW when the pixel time was set at 1.6μs. On average ~ 20% and in some cases up to 40% of the total number of Purkinje cells at this stage of development (Hamling et al., 2015; Knogler et al., 2019) were imaged.

Figure 2.18: Purkinje cells expressing GCaMP6s

A representative optical section showing GCaMP6s labelled PCs across both hemispheres of the cerebellum. Scale bar : 20μm. This image is generated by averaging all frames recorded during the experiment after motion correction.

2.7.1 Calcium trace extraction from Purkinje cells

Calcium traces were extracted from individual Purkinje cell somata using a semi-automated processing pipeline written in Python. Multi-page tiff files from two-photon imaging were loaded and corrected for translation along the X-Y plane using phase correlation with the registration module in scikit-image (Walt et al., 2014) (Figure 2.19). After motion correction, the centers of individual cells were identified manually using a GUI. A three layer neural network trained using a subset of data from these experiments was used to mark cell boundaries, guided by the manually identified center coordinates (Figure 2.20). Pixels within the ROI were averaged to obtain fluorescence intensity of each cell for a given frame. Fold change in fluorescence intensity over baseline (dF/F) was calculated with baseline estimated as the tenth percentile of the fluorescence intensity for each cell over time. In case of multi-trial experiments, the baseline was updated once for each trial. For the continuous 700s long recordings shown in Figure 4.6, baseline was calculated for each frame as the tenth percentile of a one minute window around that frame. Overlapping pixels assigned to more than one ROI were excluded from any of the assigned ROIs to avoid signal contamination from neighbouring cells. The resultant ROIs consisted of 140 ± 26 (mean \pm SD) pixels each.

Figure 2.19: Motion correction by phase correlation

Left: average image before (top) and after (bottom) motion correction of all frames acquired during an experiment. Edges are sharper post motion correction. Right: the translation in the X (orange) and Y (blue) axes detected by the motion correction algorithm, in pixel units. Sharp blips, mostly seen in the Y dimension are due to swim bouts, which tend to displace the restrained head along this axis. The slow drift in the X dimension contributes to the motion blur seen in the uncorrected image on the left.

Figure 2.20: Neural network based detection of cell boundaries

Top: Identification of cell boundaries by a neural network. Once the centers of cells have been manually marked, a radial intensity profile is obtained for the cell. A neural network then assigns one pixel along each radial profile to be the edge of the cell (red line in top right). Bottom: A full two-photon imaging plane with many cells detected. Overlapping pixels from independently detected ROIs of neighboring cells are excluded. Scale bar is 20 μ m.

2.8 Granule cell calcium imaging

Head-restrained Tg(neurod:GCaMP6f) ; nacre^{-/-} larvae were used to image granule cell calcium activity (Rupprecht et al., 2016). In order to sample a substantial proportion of all granule cells, 6 planes separated by 10 μ m were imaged in every fish, starting from the dorsal side of the GC layer (Figure 2.21A). A two-trial behavior protocol was carried out serially for each imaging plane. Since galvo scanning was used, we scanned a single hemisphere of the granule cell layer to achieve sufficient frame rate for GCaMP6f, while still densely sampling the cell population (Figure 2.21B). A 256 \times 128 pixel field of view with 0.53 μ m pixel size was scanned with a pixel time of 3.2 μ s, resulting in a frame rate of 7.8Hz. Laser power used for granule cell imaging was in the range of 15-20mW at the sample plane. Post acquisition, a 2-frame temporal averaging was used to improve signal to noise ratio to aid subsequent analysis.

2.8.1 Calcium trace extraction from granule cells

The large number of granule cells (~6000 in 7dpf larvae) made it infeasible to use the fully manual protocol used for Purkinje cells to mark centroids of cells. The behavior protocol consisted of multiple trials per optical plane imaged. X-Y motion correction was performed within each imaging plane across the multiple trials using the same algorithm as described above. The accuracy of image registration was verified manually for each trial. Centroid coordinates were loosely identified using a 2D local minimum intensity function, following which they were refined by manual pruning. Cell boundaries were then drawn automatically by detecting bright cytoplasmic GCaMP fluorescence using a threshold function applied radially around the coordinates identified (Figure 2.21C). Overlapping pixels across ROIs were excluded and dF/F was calculated for each cell using the same procedure as described for Purkinje cells.

Figure 2.21: Imaging granule cell activity across multiple planes

(A) Schematic of the multi-plane GC imaging protocol. A single hemisphere of the cerebellum (highlighted in green) is serially scanned across 6 imaging planes separated by $10\ \mu\text{m}$. (B) A representative imaging plane showing GCs labelled with GCaMP6f. Scale bar: $20\ \mu\text{m}$. (C) ROIs drawn around GC cell bodies using semi-automated anatomical segmentation.

2.9 Event triggered calcium responses

In some cases, analysis was performed on event triggered calcium responses, with or without averaging. Calcium traces were cropped and aligned around events of interest such as the onset of motor activity or the onset of a stimulus in the experimental protocol. In these plots, $t=0\text{s}$ indicates the time point of alignment. Figure 2.22 illustrates this process.

Figure 2.22: Event triggered calcium responses

(A) Calcium signal recorded from one representative cell over a 700s period. Arrows indicate hypothetical time points of interest. (B) Cropped snippets of calcium responses centered around the time points of interest. (C) Aligned raw calcium traces (grey) and their average (black). Vertical red dashed line in (C) and $t=0$ s in (B, C) represent the time point around which the traces have been aligned.

2.10 Cerebellum ablations

$Tg(\text{aldoca:GCaMP6s}) ; nacre^{-/-}$ larvae were prepared for cerebellum ablations using the same protocol as used for the calcium imaging experiments. 10 planes within the Purkinje cell layer, separated by $4\mu\text{m}$, were serially scanned with the same scanning parameters used for the imaging experiments. Ablations were confined to the Purkinje cell layer using visual aid from GCaMP fluorescence. The laser was tuned to 920nm with a power of $\sim 230\text{mW}$ at the sample plane. Each plane was scanned 10 times before moving to the next. This led to effective plasma mediated lesioning of the whole cerebellum within the region being scanned. Lesions were confirmed visually by an immediate increase in fluorescence intensity due to uncontrolled influx of calcium into the cytosol, followed by blebbing and disintegration of cells (Figure 4.7C). Fish were allowed to recover for 1 hour post lesion before initiating the behavior protocol. The cerebellum was scanned while the behavior protocol was carried out with laser power

and scan settings identical to those used for calcium imaging in non-lesioned fish to maintain experimental conditions.

2.11 Extracellular loose-patch recordings from Purkinje neurons

The electrophysiology experiments were performed by Aalok Varma. 6-7dpf zebrafish larvae were first anesthetized in 0.01% MS-222 and transferred to a recording chamber. Two pieces of fine tungsten wire (California Fine Wire) were used to pin the larvae through the notochord onto a Sylgard (Dow Corning) slab in the recording chamber. A third pin was used to orient the head dorsal side up (Fig. 5a). The MS-222 was then replaced by external solution (composition in mM: 134 NaCl, 2.9 KCl, 1.2 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 10 glucose, 2.1 CaCl₂, 0.01 d-tubocurarine; pH 7.8; 290 mOsm) and the skin covering the brain and along the tail was carefully removed using forceps (Fine Science Tools). The preparation was then taken to a rig apparatus.

Patch pipettes for loose-patch recordings were made using thick-walled borosilicate capillaries (1.5mm OD; 0.86mm ID, Warner Instruments) and pulled to 1-1.5 μ m tip diameter using a Flaming Brown P-97 pipette puller (Sutter Instruments), such that their resistance when back-filled with external solution was approximately 7-10M Ω . Similarly, suction recording pipettes for fictive motor recordings were made using thin-walled borosilicate capillaries (1.5mm OD; 1.1mm ID, Sutter Instruments), pulled to \sim 5 μ m tip diameter, such that their resistance when backfilled with external solution was 0.7-1.5M Ω .

First, ventral root recordings to monitor fictive swimming were obtained by guiding the pipette to a myotomal boundary (\sim 15-20th somite) and applying mild suction. Once a successful recording was obtained, the focus was shifted to the cerebellum and loose patch recordings from Purkinje neurons were obtained. The pipettes were guided visually using the 60x/1.0NA water immersion objective of a compound microscope (Ni-E, Nikon) and a motorized micro-manipulator (PatchStar, Scientifica). Once both pipettes were positioned, the condenser of the microscope was gently moved to allow the introduction of a 5-inch LCD screen (Adafruit) to present visual stimuli.

Visual stimulus presentation and electrophysiological recordings were triggered simultane-

ously and acquired using a Multiclamp 700B amplifier, Digidata 1440A digitizer and pCLAMP software (Molecular Devices). The data were low-pass filtered at 2kHz using a Bessel filter and sampled at 50kHz at a gain between 10-2000, adjusted depending on the quality of each recording. The ventral root recordings were parallelly acquired and real-time analysis was performed to provide closed-loop optomotor feedback as described in section 2.3.2.

2.11.1 Spike detection and analysis

Spikes were identified as events that showed large fluctuations relative to a 25ms rolling window baseline and the peak times and amplitudes were extracted. Small amplitude events were classified as simple spikes (SSs) and large amplitude events as climbing fiber (CF) inputs (Sengupta and Thirumalai, 2015). Once identified and sorted, recordings were triggered to the start of optic flow trials or probe trials. Mean firing rates for optic flow and probe trials were estimated by convolving peri-event time histograms of 20ms binwidth with a 200ms gaussian kernel. Analysis was done using custom scripts written in Python. and CF/SS event detection was done in MATLAB (<https://github.com/wagenadl/mbl-nsb-toolbox>).

2.11.2 Calcium imaging during 2D virtual navigation

Proof of concept recordings were made from the telencephalon of a head-restrained 7dpf neuroD:GCaMP6f transgenic fish (Figure 2.23). The fish was placed in a 10.5×10.5cm 2D virtual arena consisting of randomly placed black square landmark features of variable dimensions as shown in Figure 2.24 (see section 2.3.4). Optic flow was provided in order to initiate swimming by slowly translating the fish in one of four random directions. Periods where the fish did not swim resulted in slow drift in a straight line as shown in the trajectory plot in Figure 2.24. The fish made both forward swim bouts and turns in the arena, indicated by the irregular portion of the trajectory plot. Neuronal activity from the telencephalon was imaged simultaneously (Figure 2.25).

Figure 2.23: Neurons in the telencephalon expressing GCaMP6f

2.12 Data processing and analysis

Most of the data processing, all of the analysis and statistical tests were performed using Python. Spike detection for data from the electrophysiology experiments was done by Aalok Varma using Matlab.

2.13 Statistics

All statistical tests were performed in Python using SciPy (Virtanen et al., 2020) and statsmodels (Seabold and Perktold, 2010) and scikit-posthocs (Terpilowski, 2019). The statistical tests used and their results are mentioned in the figure legends.

Figure 2.25: Calcium responses of cells in the telencephalon of the fish as it navigated the 2D arena

2.14 References

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Chapter 3

Role of the cerebellum in expectation-dependent adaptation of motor output

3.1 Introduction

Motor control is one of the primary functions performed by the brain (Grillner and El Manira, 2020). Once a motor command has been generated, it goes through multiple synaptic steps where errors can accumulate, before the movement finally occurs (Shadmehr et al., 2010). Moreover, while movements are being executed, unexpected changes in the environment, such as while walking on uneven terrain, leads to errors unless sensory feedback is used to correct for them. The sensory feedback is also delayed and often imperfect (Shadmehr et al., 2010; Körding and Wolpert, 2004). Despite these challenges, motor systems perform exceedingly well in achieving precisely coordinated error-free movements (Grillner and El Manira, 2020; Shadmehr et al., 2010). To achieve this, it is widely believed that the brain encodes internal models of the motor system and the environment. A 'forward model' is used to predict the sensory consequences of a given motor command before it is executed and corrections are introduced prior to the execution of the movement (Grillner and El Manira, 2020; Shadmehr et al., 2010; Wolpert and Flanagan, 2016). Once the movement is made, predictions of the model are evaluated against their real world consequences and corrections are introduced to ongoing movements. If the same errors occur consistently, the model itself is adapted, such that the future predictions it makes can be more accurate. By this process, the brain learns to generate arbitrarily complex, yet error-free movements.

The cerebellum is a highly conserved vertebrate brain region which is believed to play a central role in model based control of movements. Several theoretical models of motor control have been proposed, inspired by its circuit architecture and based on experimental observations (Marr, 1969; Albus, 1971; Wolpert and Kawato, 1998; Dean et al., 2010). The classical view of cerebellar function states that through a mechanism of synaptic depression, parallel fiber (PF)

inputs that contribute to Purkinje cell activity coincident with errors are eliminated. According to this framework, the PF inputs to Purkinje cells are thought to expansively encode sensory and motor variables and the climbing fiber (CF) inputs from the inferior olive are thought to signal errors. Therefore, by suppressing those PF synapses that are co-active when the CFs are active, the cerebellum learns to filter PF response types that contribute to error-free movements (Ito, 2000; Marr, 1969; Albus, 1971). While there have been several experimental observations in support of this mechanism (Narain et al., 2018; Herzfeld et al., 2018), how it acts across the scale of the circuit to generate complex movements is not well known (Khilkevich et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2020). In addition to adaptive filtering of the PF inputs to Purkinje cells, it is also possible that error signals from the inferior olive induce learning at the level of the output neurons of the cerebellum (Shadmehr, 2020). Here, we set out to study the role of the cerebellum in adaptive locomotor behavior in larval zebrafish.

Previous studies have shown that head-restrained larval zebrafish adapt their motor output to changes in gain in a closed-loop optomotor environment (Portugues and Engert, 2011; Ahrens et al., 2012). When the inferior olive was lesioned in one of these studies, adaptation to gain change did not take place (Ahrens et al., 2012), suggesting a role for the cerebellar circuitry in this process. A subsequent study showed that integration of error by the dorsal raphe nucleus could explain both within-bout and across-bout changes in motor vigor in response to gain change. However, questions still remain on the role of the inferior olive and the cerebellum in this process and how computations performed by the dorsal raphe nucleus integrate with motor command generation (Kawashima et al., 2016). We performed gain adaptation experiments in a closed-loop optomotor environment (see methods) to quantify the behavioral features of adaptation in detail and gain a better understanding of the underlying mechanisms involved by analysing simultaneously recorded Purkinje cell population activity. To adapt to closed-loop gain changes, it is required that the fish brain compares an expectation of the consequence of motor commands with their real world consequences, as detected by sensory feedback from the visual system. This comparison would result in mismatch or error signals, which can be used to inform corrective strategies. Based on the fact that the cerebellum plays a prominent role in such forms of adaptation (see paragraph above), we hypothesized that the error signal would

be present in the olivary inputs to Purkinje cells and set out to perform calcium imaging experiments to detect it. Shortly after preliminary experiments were conducted, Kawashima et al. (2016) showed that the mismatch signal that drives gain adaptation is likely to be computed in the dorsal raphe nucleus in the fish brain.

This chapter presents detailed analysis of the behavioral features of gain adaptation in larval zebrafish. At the end of the chapter, preliminary results from Purkinje cell population imaging during the adaptation protocol are discussed. Moreover, the fact that fish adapted to changes in gain also serves as a validation of the custom made closed-loop behavioral setup, which has been used extensively in the rest of the thesis.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Larval zebrafish adapt motor output to compensate for changes in closed-loop gain

Behavior experiments were performed to analyse how larval zebrafish adapt to change in gain of the closed-loop feedback (see section 2.3.2). These experiments were performed on head-restrained 7-day old larval zebrafish. Fish were subjected to a gain change protocol where the closed-loop gain was varied. Each gain setting lasted for a period of 10s and looped between 1, 2 and 0.5 in that order (Figure 3.2). This block of three gains was repeated multiple times for each fish (5x for protocol with no rest, 20x for protocol with rest). A forward optic flow stimulus of 1cm/s was provided to initiate swims. Some experiments were carried out with no gap between each gain setting (N = 5 fish). Rest of the experiments were carried out with a 10s gap in which stationary gratings were presented, in open-loop, between changes in gain (N = 4 fish). A gain of 1 would result in realistic optomotor coupling between motor output of the fish and the resultant forward velocity in the virtual world (Figure 3.1, see section 2.3.2). We analysed the effect of changing gain by a factor of 2 higher or lower with respect to the realistic gain of 1. If fish indeed used visual feedback to assess the consequence of their actions to correct for errors, we would expect motor output to adapt to produce stronger and/or more frequent swims in the low gain setting and vice-versa in the high gain setting. Figure 3.2 shows swim velocity for a representative set of consecutive trials in one fish across the three gain

settings. The traces shown in this figure are the closed-loop swim velocity divided by the gain factor. The resultant value after dividing by gain is the scaled instantaneous swim strength, representing the strength/vigor of tail movement at every time point, which can be compared across gain settings (see equation in section 2.3.2). Adaptation of swim strength to changes in gain is apparent in these plots.

Figure 3.1: Schematic of the closed-loop optomotor environment showing the effect of gain on virtual swim velocity

Figure 3.2: Gain normalized swim velocity traces showing adaptation of motor output

Left: Protocols with (bottom) and without rest (top) used in the adaptation assay. Right: representative gain normalized swim velocity traces. Discrete bouts of swimming can be seen with adaptation visible in bout duration, velocity, and inter-bout interval.

3.2.2 Adaptation involves regulation of strength and frequency of swim bouts

To compare motor behavior across different fish, the parameters quantified were normalized with respect to their average value at gain 1. Data from both sets of experiments (with and without rest) have been pooled since no significant differences were observed between them. The schematic in Figure 3.3 shows how swim bout parameters have been quantified.

Figure 3.3: Quantifying swim bout parameters

Adaptation was observed in all swim parameters that were quantified. Swim bout strength, which is defined as the area under the gain normalized swim velocity trace, showed the strongest effect. Modulation of bout strength occurred through correlated changes in bout duration and velocity. A sharp reduction in inter-bout interval was seen in the gain 0.5 setting, whereas gain 1 and 2 had comparable interval between bouts. No trend was observed in the total number of bouts, most likely due to the opposing contributions of inter-bout interval and bout duration to the total bout count. These effects were also apparent in histograms of data from individual fish.

In Figure 3.4, the left column (panels A, D, G, J) shows probability densities of pooled parameters across all 9 fish. The middle column (panels B, E, H, K) shows representative histograms of bout parameters for one fish. The same trends in bout parameter distribution can be observed in both pooled data and in the representative histograms. The third column on the right (panels C, F, I, L, M) shows means of the parameter distributions estimated individually for each fish. Gray lines are individual fish and black is the average. Error bars represent SEM across fish. ** : $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ by Friedman's test.

Figure 3.4: Larval zebrafish adapt motor output to compensate for gain change in closed-loop

3.2.3 Regulation of motor output begins within the first swim bout post gain change

Adaptation of motor output to closed-loop gain change can be explained by two underlying mechanisms, either acting on their own or in combination with one another. Fish are able to determine that the closed-loop gain has changed by evaluating the visual feedback generated by a swim bout. This feedback can be used online, within each bout as they occur, to update the ongoing bout to correct for error. Each swim bout could therefore keep correcting for its own error and there may be no 'learning' taking place across-bouts. Alternatively, visual feedback may not be used to correct the ongoing swim bout, possibly because computing error (how different is the expected swim velocity from the actual value) and updating the motor command may not be performed within the time frame of individual bouts. The error could rather be used to update an internal 'set-point' that determines the relationship between motor output and forward velocity so that future swim bouts are error free. It is also possible that both these processes occur together, with online feedback enabling adaptation within the first bout in a new gain and an internal re-calibration leading to progressively less error as more swim bouts are generated. Both these mechanisms require an internal model that predicts the expected sensory consequence of the motor command being executed.

To test whether fish use visual feedback to correct for motor errors within an ongoing swim bout, we looked at the first swim bout post gain change (Figure 3.5). In these experiments, gain changes always took place in a fixed, repetitive order : 1 to 2 to 0.5, then back to 1 again and so on. The first swim bout in all gains deviated from the average in the previous gain and tended towards the average bout in the current gain (Figure 3.5). This indicates that fish correct for motor errors within an ongoing swim bout using immediate visual feedback. However, the strength of the first bout was between what was observed in the previous gain and the current gain, indicating that there was also a component of adaptation that acted over multiple bouts.

Figure 3.5: Adaptation begins within the first bout in a new gain

Top row: gain normalized swim velocity traces from a representative fish showing the first bout in the current gain (black) and the last bout in the previous gain (red). The current and previous gains are indicated within each panel. Traces have been triggered at 50ms prior to the onset of each bout. Bottom row: the average swim strength of bouts in the previous gain (grey), of only the first bout in the current gain (red) and all bouts in the current gain (black). Error bars represent the SEM across fish.

3.2.4 Adaptation to gain change takes place over multiple swim bouts

Next, we looked at the progression of bout strength over the first 8 bouts post gain change. A slow component of adaptation which developed over 5-6 swim bouts could be seen. This indicates that there indeed is a lasting update of an internal model which determines the relationship between a motor command and its expected consequence.

Figure 3.6: Adaptation develops over many swim bouts

A) Bout-wise progression of adaptation post gain change. Solid lines are averages of $N=9$ fish and shaded regions are SEM. B-D) Same data represented in A shown separately for each gain setting. Dark lines represent the average and lighter lines are individual fish. The y-axis in B-D are scaled according to each gain to better visualize the progression of adaptation.

3.2.5 Neural mechanisms underlying motor adaptation

The results presented above show that the larval zebrafish brain encodes an internal model of the expected consequence of a motor command. If the sensory feedback of a motor command do not match the predictions generated by this model, corrections are added to minimize the mismatch. In these experiments, this is likely done by evaluating whether the expected instantaneous forward velocity is achieved by the ongoing movement and if not, corrections are introduced to the ongoing movement. In order to estimate whether there are motor errors, a comparison between the expected sensory feedback and actual sensory feedback is necessary. Any discrepancy between the two during this comparison would lead to an error signal, whose magnitude and sign can be used in a hypothetical control loop to add an appropriate corrective component to the ongoing motor command.

Apart from correcting errors when movements occur, we also see an updating of the internal

model over time, across many swim bouts. This indicates that the error signal is also used to re-calibrate the internal model if it repeatedly generates incorrect predictions. This behavioral assay allows for investigations into both these processes, namely how error signals are computed and used to correct ongoing movements and how persistent errors lead to an update of the internal model, possibly through mechanisms involving short and long term learning.

3.2.6 Calcium activity in a subset of Purkinje cells is correlated with gain

To investigate the underlying neural mechanisms involved, we focused on the cerebellum, which is a brain region shown to be involved in model-based control of motor output over a range of timescales. Preliminary experiments were performed in which we imaged Purkinje cell calcium activity in Tg(aldoca:GCaMP6s) ; nacre^{-/-} fish, while they adapted to changes in closed-loop gain.

In these experiments, fish were presented with 25 trials of an adaptation protocol, while two-photon imaging was carried out. The protocol began with a 10s period of no optic flow, after which a 10s period of 1cm/s forward optic flow stimuli was presented at gain 1. Next, after a gap of 10s with no flow, another 10s of forward optic flow was presented at either gain 0.5 or 2, chosen randomly. We then looked for cells whose activity was significantly different between the initial gain of 1 period and the next gain. Preliminary analysis was carried out to identify cells whose activity correlated with gain. In this analysis, the area under the calcium activity trace within each gain setting was compared using a t-test and cells that consistently showed higher or lower activity in gain of 0.5 or 2 w.r.t. gain 1 were identified. A total of 15 cells, out of 97 cells from 2 fish, were identified using this method. Out of these 15, 5 cells showed a modulation on gain decrease, 4 to an increase in gain and the remaining 6 showed consistent modulation to both gain increase and decrease. The modulation could either be a decrease or increase in calcium activity for an individual cell.

This analysis however does not reveal what cells encode when they show a gain-correlated change in activity. Their activity could be related to either optic flow, motor activity, self generated closed-loop optic flow, motor errors or a combination of these variables. To better

understand the underlying mechanism, a multi-step calcium imaging protocol must be carried out. First, the tuning properties of each cell to sensory input and motor parameters at a gain of 1 can be determined by providing optic flow stimuli in both forward and backward directions at varying velocities. Regression based analysis, as used in the subsequent chapter, can be used to determine the motor and sensory tuning of each cell. After this step, an adaptation protocol can be carried out to analyse the responses of like-tuned cells to gain change.

Figure 3.7: Some Purkinje cells show gain correlated modulation of calcium activity

A) Schematic of the adaptation protocol. B) A representative image of the Purkinje cell layer imaged in one fish. Scale bar : 20 μ m. C) Protocol used to identify gain modulated cells. D) Representative traces of individual gain modulated cells from one fish. Top row : a cell that showed increased activity in low gain (left) and another cell that showed decreased activity in low gain (right). Bottom row : a cell that showed increased activity in high gain (left) and another cell that showed decreased activity in high gain. Gray lines are single trial responses and black is the average response of each cell.

3.3 Summary

These experiments show that larval zebrafish adapt their motor output in response to gain changes in closed-loop feedback. They show both fast, within bout correction of motor output, as well as longer term adaptation that builds up over multiple swim bouts. This indicates that

they re-calibrate an internal model using sensory feedback to be able to correctly predict the consequence of motor commands. Preliminary calcium imaging experiments suggest a role for the cerebellum in this process but further experiments, like the ones suggested above, are necessary to understand its role in gain adaptation.

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Chapter 4

Stimulus expectation drives cerebellum-mediated predictive control of the optomotor response in larval zebrafish

4.1 Highlights

- Larval zebrafish learn to expect repeatedly encountered optic flow stimuli
- Stimulus history over minutes contributes to an internal model of the sensory world
- Purkinje neuron activity encodes deviations from expected direction of optic flow
- The cerebellum uses learnt expectations to generate lower latency swim responses

4.2 Abstract

The cerebellum is known to optimize behavioral responses via error minimization, yet how past sensory experience shapes cerebellar output is still poorly understood. We imaged cerebellar Purkinje cells (PCs) in larval zebrafish during a behavioral assay in which they learnt to expect the direction of optic flow stimulus. PCs encoded signals of expectation and a graded error signal when a deviant stimulus was encountered. The amplitude of the error signal scaled based on stimulus history over minute-timescales. Granule cells (GC) did not encode error, however, some GC types encoded putative expectation signals. When PC population-wide readouts of expectation and error signals were strong, swim latency was low and vice versa, indicating participation of these signals in motor planning. Consistent with this, lesioning the cerebellum abolished expectation-dependent modulation of swim latency. Based on these results we propose that PCs use expectation and error signals to acquire and update internal models of the world.

4.3 Introduction

A hallmark of animal behavior is the ability to learn fast and adapt to changing environments. With experience, animals across species can learn to expect events such as rewards or threats and predict the consequences of their actions (Claudi et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2020; Wagner et al., 2017). By integrating sensory evidence as and when available, the brain builds up an internal model of the world, which can be used to generate predictions to guide behavior. Neural mechanisms involved in this process often use error feedback to adaptively update models when the predictions they generate do not match outcomes in the real world (Schultz and Dickinson, 2000). The cerebellum is a highly conserved brain region shown to be involved in this process but we do not yet have a circuit-wide understanding of the neural mechanisms involved. The primary input layer to the cerebellum is composed of a large number of granule cells (GCs), which are thought to expansively encode sensory and motor related inputs. Output from many GCs converge onto downstream Purkinje cells (PC). It is believed that by depressing GC synapses co-active with error signals from the inferior olive (IO), PCs learn to selectively respond to GC inputs that lead to error-free behavior (Albus, 1971; Ito, 2000; Marr, 1969).

Cerebellar function has been historically studied in the context of motor planning, learning and control (Chabrol et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2018; Herzfeld et al., 2018; Markov et al., 2021; Narayanan and Thirumalai, 2019; Wolpert and Kawato, 1998). It is widely believed that with experience, the cerebellum learns how to control movements by acquiring predictive models of the motor system and the environment (Markov et al., 2021; Narayanan and Thirumalai, 2019; Wolpert and Kawato, 1998). Recently, the predictive functions of the cerebellum have been shown to be more generally applicable to non-motor domains, such as in encoding the expectation of rewards (Hull, 2020; Kostadinov et al., 2019; Larry et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2017). Here, using a novel optomotor assay consisting of familiar and deviant optic flow stimuli, we probed whether the larval zebrafish cerebellum is involved in learning to expect stimuli based prior experience over behaviorally relevant timescales of seconds to minutes.

The cerebellum is one of the oldest parts of the vertebrate brain, with cell types and connectivity well conserved in all vertebrates from fish to mammals (Bae et al., 2009; Bell et al.,

2008). In larval zebrafish, the cerebellum is functional by 5 days post-fertilization (dpf) concomitant with the emergence of motor behaviors (Sengupta and Thirumalai, 2015). At these stages, its small size and transparency allows the imaging of a substantial proportion of all cells in the cerebellum. By analysing the activity of both PCs and GCs in the same context from different fish, we hoped to arrive at a mechanistic description of cerebellar function. Previous studies have shown that the larval zebrafish cerebellum is involved in associative learning as seen in other species (Harmon et al., 2017) and pre-motor activity in the fish cerebellum predicts future swim decisions (Lin et al., 2020), indicating a role in motor planning. PCs in larval zebrafish perform a combination of sensory and motor functions and are strongly activated by optic flow stimuli (Knogler et al., 2019; Scalise et al., 2016). The behavioral relevance of optic flow to fish means that no prior training is required, giving us the opportunity to probe innate mechanisms that enable them to learn what to expect from the sensory world.

Larval zebrafish sense optic flow and generate compensatory swims in the same direction (optomotor response or OMR) (Naumann et al., 2016; Neuhauss et al., 1999; Orger et al., 2000). The OMR is believed to help them stabilize their position in flowing water and can be reliably evoked in head-restrained fish by providing optic flow stimuli in the caudo-rostral direction on a screen placed beneath them (Portugues and Engert, 2011). The latency with which optomotor swims are initiated depends strongly on the optic flow velocity (Portugues et al., 2015; Severi et al., 2014). Apart from velocity, previous studies in both restrained and free swimming fish have also shown that the decision to swim is driven by a leaky integration of visual input, which is used to determine the direction of optic flow, especially in case of sparse and noisy environments (Bahl and Engert, 2020). So far, these studies have looked at the OMR from a sensori-motor point of view and the contribution of learnt biases to this behavior has not been investigated. Here, we sought to ask whether the OMR is also influenced by a learnt expectation based on prior experience with optic flow stimuli.

In this study, we conducted a series of experiments on head-restrained larval zebrafish in a closed-loop optomotor environment, while simultaneously imaging calcium activity of specific cell types in the cerebellum. By introducing deviant stimuli after acclimatization to repetitive

forward optic flow pulses, we probed whether fish learnt to expect the direction of optic flow stimulus. Our results indicate a causal role for the cerebellar circuit and directionally-tuned PCs in particular in signaling deviation from an expected pattern and in planning the motor response. We find that through this mechanism, larval zebrafish acquire internal models of their sensory world from experience, update these models when deviations occur and adjust their motor behavior accordingly.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Purkinje cells (PCs) exhibit direction tuned responses to optic flow

To characterize the response properties of PCs to optic flow stimuli, we recorded calcium activity in head-restrained larval zebrafish swimming in a one dimensional closed-loop optomotor environment using two-photon microscopy (Figure 4.1A,B). Fish were initially presented with randomly interspersed pulses of 2s duration, of forward (+ve) or backward (-ve) moving gratings at 1cm/s or a ‘probe’ stimulus, where the gratings moved 1 pixel on the screen in the forward (+ve probe) or backward (-ve probe) direction, 4 times over the 2s (Figure 4.1C). Each stimulus was presented five times per fish with an interval of 5s between them (Figure 4.1C). We then fit the calcium responses of individual cells using forward, backward and motor regressors using multiple linear regression and selected cells whose responses could be fit with an $R^2 \geq 0.6$ (Figure 4.1D) (Knogler et al., 2019; Miri et al., 2010). When we grouped cells based on the largest regression coefficient, we found that they segregated into either ‘forward’ or ‘backward’ tuned (Figure S4.1A) and there were no cells that were strongly activated by both directions of optic flow (Figure S4.1A,D). These results are consistent with previous findings which show that PC response to optic flow is direction specific (Knogler et al., 2019). Fewer cells were activated the strongest during motor activity and not by optic flow stimuli. The motor correlated cells were also typically activated by forward optic flow stimuli (Figure 4.1E). This could be because of two reasons: since forward optic flow stimuli reliably evoked swims, PCs involved in generating the optomotor response could be activated by both sensory input as well as motor activity. Or, the strong correlation between motor activity and the forward optic flow stimulus could make it difficult to distinguish between them using regression.

We then proceeded to classify cells as either ‘forward’, ‘backward’ or ‘motor’ based on the largest regression coefficient and strong correlation (Pearson’s $r \geq 0.6$) with the respective regressor. Using this approach, we were able to classify $24 \pm 12\%$ (mean \pm SD) of all cells (796 cells from 8 fish) in one of the three groups. This classification was used in subsequent trials to group cells based on their tuning. Optic flow stimuli in both the forward (+ve) and backward (-ve) directions at 1cm/s caused strong activation in distinct populations of PCs (Figure 4.1E column 1,3). Both the positive and negative probe stimuli, being on average 15 times weaker than the 1cm/s optic flow stimuli, caused a much lower but detectable activation in PCs (Figure 4.1E column 2,4). Responses to the probe stimuli were also direction tuned, even though these stimuli consisted only of suggestive 1 pixel shifts in grating position, corresponding to a 3.2° visual angle, in the forward or backward direction (Figure 4.1E column 2,4). Forward moving gratings at 1cm/s reliably evoked swims. There were rarely any swims in response to the probe stimuli. Backward moving gratings at 1cm/s either failed to induce swim responses or caused struggles and/or large amplitude turns and hence were not presented subsequently.

Figure 4.1: Purkinje cells show direction selective responses to optic flow stimuli

(A) Schematic of the experimental setup. (B) Average two-photon image of PCs expressing GCaMP6s from a representative fish. Scale bar : 20μm (C) Left: zoomed in view of the stimulus protocol highlighting the 5s interval between two stimulus pulses and the 2s pulse duration. Right: an example of the randomly ordered optic flow stimulus presented in the first trial. Note: the y-axis is scaled non-linearly in this schematic to highlight the small amplitude 'probe stimulus' pulses. (D) Classification of PCs based on tuning as backward (black), forward (magenta) or motor (brown) using regressors (gray) in a representative fish, shown as mean ± SD. (E) Average response profiles across fish of backward, forward and motor tuned cells (rows 2, 3 and 4 respectively) aligned to the start of each stimulus (column 1-4) or motor activity

(column 5); shaded regions around the average calcium traces are SEM over N=8 fish. The first row shows the respective optic flow stimulus (columns 1-4) and average motor activity (column 5). Motor activity traces in gray represent the average for individual fish.

4.4.2 Response to optic flow in PCs is modulated by stimulus history

After the first trial where stimuli were presented in random order (Figures 4.1C, 2A), subsequent trials in the next phase of the experiment were conducted to test whether stimulus history influences PC response to deviant optic flow stimuli. We acclimatized fish with 8 repetitions of 2s long forward optic flow stimuli at 1cm/s, which consistently evoked slow forward swims in closed-loop (Figure 4.2B-E). The trials then proceeded into a probe phase where different probe stimuli were presented as shown in Figure 4.2A. These stimuli were either 3 pulses of the negative probe stimulus, 3 pulses of the positive probe stimulus or stationary gratings (no probe). In addition to these trials, a fourth trial was included where acclimatization pulses were presented at randomized time intervals (range: 1.5-8.5s, mean: 5s) instead of the fixed 5s interval. This was followed by 3 pulses of the negative probe stimulus. Each of the trials were presented three times in a different randomized order for every fish and the responses were averaged by trial type for each cell. We then analyzed the effect of acclimatization on the response to probe stimuli, with respect to baseline responses measured when stimuli were presented in random order in the first trial.

In backward-tuned cells, post acclimatization, the response to negative probe stimulus showed a large amplitude increase compared to baseline (Figure 4.2B,F,G). This enhanced response exhibited a decay over multiple presentations of the probe stimulus and approached baseline levels (Figure 4.2B,C). The increase in response amplitude was present to an equivalent extent when the timing of the acclimatization stimulus was randomized, indicating that timing did not play a role in the enhancement of the probe response (Figure 4.2C,G). Positive probe stimuli evoked no detectable calcium events in these cells (Figure 4.2D,G). In forward-tuned cells, negative probe stimuli evoked no response, whereas, positive probe stimuli showed no enhancement with respect to baseline (Figure 4.2H, S4.2). Both forward tuned and backward tuned cells did not show any responses when stationary gratings were presented in the

probe phase (Figures 4.2E,G,H, S4.2C). Collectively, these results point to history-dependent enhancement of directionally-tuned PC responses. Specifically, in backward-tuned PCs, weak backward flows during random presentation evoked a small response; the same stimulus after the fish was acclimatized with forward flows evoked an enhanced response in the same PCs. It is possible that the enhanced response to the probe stimulus encodes a deviation from expected optic flow direction.

Figure 4.2: A change in optic flow direction is encoded in enhanced responses to probe stimuli

(A) Schematic of the experimental protocol. Trials 2-13 began with an acclimatization phase of 8x 1cm/s optic flow pulses followed by a probe phase. (B-E) Average calcium responses in the backward tuned cells to the different trials (B: negative probe, C: random stimulus timing followed by negative probe, D: positive probe and E: no probe). The respective optic flow stimuli and average motor activity are shown above. Individual calcium traces in gray are the responses of individual fish (N=8). Fold-change in peak amplitude in response to the three presentations of the negative probe stimuli w.r.t the baseline amplitude in trial 1 are shown for (B) and (C). ** : $p < 0.01$ and * : $p < 0.05$ by Wilcoxon signed-rank test showing an elevation in amplitude w.r.t baseline (dashed line at 0). There were no large calcium responses in the backward tuned cells to the positive probe or the zero probe (D, E). (F) Average calcium response in backward tuned cells to the negative probe stimulus when presented in random order in trial 1 (gray) and to the first presentation of the same stimulus post acclimatization (black) showing the enhancement of the calcium response post acclimatization. (G, H) The peak amplitude in dF/F of the trial averaged calcium response to the respective stimuli shown on the x-axis for the backward tuned cells (G) and the forward tuned cells (H). * : $p < 0.05$ w.r.t the baseline amplitude by post-hoc Conover's test following a significant Friedman's test ($p = 3 \times 10^{-5}$). N=8 fish in (G), N=7 fish in (H). No large calcium responses were seen in

forward tuned cells to any of the probe stimuli (Figure S4.2) and hence no statistical analysis was performed on the amplitude values.

4.4.3 Self generated change in optic flow due to closed-loop motor activity does not cause strong PC activation

Motor activity in closed-loop often caused a sharp change in optic flow direction. We asked if the enhanced probe response was also observed when the fish's own swimming resulted in comparable or larger backward grating movement. If a self induced reversal of optic flow direction caused a comparable activation of PCs as the negative probe stimulus, it would indicate that the response simply encoded a sensory change irrespective of what caused it. On the other hand, if the enhanced PC response to the negative probe stimulus indeed represented an unexpected externally imposed change, we would not expect to see strong activation in backward tuned PCs.

Forward moving gratings at 1cm/s reliably evoked swims. Occasional swim bouts were observed in response to the positive probe stimulus in some fish. Both the negative probe stimulus and stationary grating did not evoke swim responses (Figure 4.3A,B). In closed-loop, the net optic flow stimulus presented to the fish is the difference between the externally provided optic flow stimulus and the virtual swim velocity of the fish (Figure 4.3C) (See Methods). On average, the net optic flow stimulus seen by the fish showed a sharp dip below zero during swim bouts (Figure 4.3D) and the amplitude of the negative component was much greater during swims than the amplitude of the probe stimulus (Figure 4.3D,E). The amplitude of the calcium response in backward tuned cells to the motor activity triggered reversal of optic flow direction was negligible compared to the response to the negative probe stimulus (Figure 4.3D,E).

To compare the two, we selected swim bouts that lasted 750ms or more, corresponding to 3 calcium imaging frames, providing a sizable window for comparison of calcium activity. The average amplitude of the self generated negative optic flow was much greater than the negative probe amplitude (Figure 4.3F,G). However, the amplitude of the calcium signal was greater in response to the probe stimulus than during swim events longer than 750ms (Figure 4.3H).

Similarly, the slope of the calcium signal measured over 3 imaging frames from the onset of the probe stimulus was also greater than that in the case of swim events (Figure 4.3I).

These results show that sensory tuned PCs are not activated by self generated sensory input. The enhanced response to the negative probe stimulus indeed encodes an externally triggered deviation in optic flow direction.

Figure 4.3: Self induced change in optic flow direction does not cause PC activation

(A) Average motor activity (bottom, red) during 1cm/s forward optic flow, negative probe, positive probe and no optic flow stimuli (top, green). (B) Forward optic flow reliably evoked swims, whereas very few and no swims were seen in response to positive probe and negative probe stimuli respectively. N=8 fish, ** : $p = 0.0006$ by Friedman's test, $p = 0.011$ (forward

flow vs +ve probe) and $p = 0.002$ (forward flow vs -ve probe) by post-hoc Conover's test. (C) Example 1cm/s forward optic flow stimulus (top), motor activity (middle) and the resultant net optic flow experienced by the fish in closed-loop (bottom). (D) Average optic flow experienced by the fish during all swim bouts (top) and co-aligned calcium responses in backward tuned PCs (bottom). (E) Average optic flow stimulus experienced by the fish during negative probe pulses (zoomed inset shows the probe pulse) (top) and co-aligned calcium responses in backward tuned PCs (bottom). Gray traces represent the average response for individual fish. (F) Average optic flow experienced by the fish during swim bouts ≥ 0.75 s in duration (top) and co-aligned calcium responses in backward tuned PCs (bottom). (G) Magnitude of the negative component of optic flow during swims is much larger than the amplitude of the negative probe stimulus. (H) Peak amplitude of the calcium response in backward tuned cells to the negative probe stimulus is much larger than the response to swim bouts. (I) The slope of the rise phase of the calcium response in backward tuned cells is significantly steeper for the negative probe stimulus than during motor activity. $N=7$ fish, * : $p = 0.016$ (G, H) and 0.03 (I) by Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

4.4.4 PC response to an abrupt change in optic flow stimulus encodes deviation from expectation

If fish indeed learnt what stimulus to expect, we hypothesized that the level of confidence they have in what to expect from the sensory world would be reflected in a correspondingly scaled enhancement of the PC response to deviant stimuli. To test this hypothesis, we designed an experiment where we attempted to induce varying levels of confidence by varying the number of repetitions of the acclimatization stimulus. In this experiment, in trial 1, we presented forward and backward flows in random sequence as we did before (Figure 4.1C). Following this, we paired behaviorally salient 1cm/s forward optic flow with the negative probe stimulus. Fish were presented with a set of four trials, repeated 3x each, in random order as shown in Figure 4.4A. Each trial began with a pre-acclimatization phase ('*pre-acc*') of 3 pulses of the negative probe stimulus, followed by an acclimatization phase of either 2, 4, 8, or 16 pulses of forward moving gratings, followed by a post-acclimatization phase ('*post-acc*') of 3 pulses of the negative probe stimulus (Figure 4.4A). The trials were separated by a 30s inter-trial interval (ITI) during which stationary gratings were presented. We identified backward-tuned PCs from their responses during trial 1 and then analyzed the *pre-acc* and *post-acc* probe responses of these cells after 16, 8, 4 or 2 acclimatization pulses.

There was no change in response amplitude across all trials in the *pre-acc* phase (Figure

4.4C). The *post-acc* responses indeed scaled with the number of acclimatization pulses (Figure 4.4A-D). The response amplitude to the first probe pulse in the post phase increased on average 2-fold with increasing number of repetitions of the acclimatization stimulus. The scaling was non-linear and the population average followed a logarithmic trend. The increase in amplitude was visually apparent starting from 2 acclimatization pulses and became statistically significant with 4 or more pulses. The scaling approached saturation at 16 acclimatization pulses (Figure 4.4D). To rule out the possibility that the scaling depended only on the elapsed time between the *pre-acc* phase and the *post-acc* phase, we looked at the effect of the 35s interval (30s ITI + 5s inter-pulse delay) between the end of a trial and the first pre-probe pulse of the next trial and compared that to the scaling caused by the 4-pulse acclimatization, which spanned an equivalent duration (33s between probe pulses) (Figure S4.3A,C). Stationary gratings presented during the ITI did not lead to an enhancement of the response compared to the 4-pulse acclimatization (Figure S4.3B,D,E), nor was the response post stationary gratings significantly different from the baseline response to the negative probe stimulus when presented in random order (Figure S4.3F). These results indicate that the enhancement of PC response to probe depends on repetitive experience with the acclimatization stimulus, suggesting that fish have formed an experience based expectation of what stimulus they are likely to encounter.

A possible explanation is that the enhanced responses to deviant stimuli could be the result of accumulation of stimulus history by integration of sensory input with long time constants, representing a prior belief in what stimulus to expect. Future inputs are then evaluated with respect to this prior belief, leading to enhanced responses when deviations are encountered. To test this hypothesis, we presented a separate set of fish with a constant 1cm/s forward optic flow stimulus in the acclimatization phase, for an equivalent time duration as in the pulsed acclimatization experiments (Figure S4.4A). A constant optic flow acclimatization stimulus did not lead to an enhanced *post-acc* response with respect to pre-acc responses (Figure S4.4B-D) and the post responses were significantly lower in amplitude than the corresponding pulsed acclimatization stimuli (Figure S4.4E). These results show that the underlying mechanism is not based on a simple integration of sensory input.

Alternatively, the enhanced response to deviant stimuli could be based on an experience gated updating of what to expect from the sensory world. If this were indeed the case, we expected two properties to be exhibited by the *post-acc* response. First, multiple presentations of the probe stimulus would lead to a decay of the enhanced response till it comes back to the baseline sensory response amplitude. And second, the degree of enhancement of the response to the first *post-acc* stimulus must be independent of delay from the acclimatization phase as no updates to the expectation have been made during the delay period.

When we looked at the *post-acc* responses, there was indeed a significant decay in amplitude from the first to the third presentation of the probe stimulus. The amplitude of the *post-acc* response decayed back to the *pre-acc* levels in the 4-pulse and 2-pulse acclimatization trials (Figure 4.4E). Next, to test whether the enhancement of the response to probe decayed on its own or if it required fish to experience the probe stimulus, we conducted a separate experiment on a different group of fish. No *pre-acc* probe pulses were presented in this experiment. Fish were acclimatized to 8 pulses of 1cm/s forward optic flow, followed by 3 probe stimulus pulses, separated by 5s each. The delay to the first probe pulse from the last acclimatization pulse was varied from 1 to 15s as shown in Figure 4.4F. The amplitude of the response to the first probe pulse was independent of the delay from the acclimatization phase (Figure 4.4G,H) and exhibited a decay over the three repeats of the probe stimulus (Figures 4.4G, S4.5). These results show that the expectation is updated with experience and does not decay with time, within the limits of the 15s window. There being no change in amplitude of the response to the first probe also suggests that fish learn what stimulus they are likely to encounter rather than the time at which it would occur.

Taken together, the above results suggest that larval zebrafish learn to expect optic flow stimuli they are likely to encounter based on stimulus history over minute-timescales. A deviant probe stimulus caused enhanced responses in PCs, which scaled with the number of repetitions of the acclimatization stimulus. This enhanced response decayed back to baseline with repeated presentations of the probe stimulus and represents an error in expectation, which is likely to play a role in updating an internal model of the sensory world as new evidence is encountered.

Figure 4.4: Probe response in PCs encodes deviation from the expected direction of optic flow

(A) Top (text): description of the experimental protocol. Middle: 3x probe pulses presented before (pre) and after (post) acclimatization pulses of forward optic flow at 1 cm/s. The number of acclimatization pulses was varied (16, 8, 4 or 2) and these blocks were presented in randomized order. Bottom: Corresponding calcium responses in backward tuned cells. Solid line is the mean for $N=7$ fish and shaded regions are SEM. Colors indicate the number of acclimatization pulses. (B) Zoomed in view of the average calcium response of backward tuned cells to pre- (left) and post-probe (right) pulses aligned to the onset of the first probe. (C) Average amplitude of the response to pre-probe stimuli. ns : $p = 0.54$. The 3 probe pulses were pooled as there was no difference between them. (D) Average amplitude of the response to the first post-probe pulse scales with the number of acclimatization pulses. $p = 0.0015$ by Friedman's

test, * : $p < 0.05$, ** : $p < 0.01$ by post-hoc Conover's test w.r.t the pre-probe amplitude. (E) Decay of the amplitude of the enhanced response to the post-probe stimulus over the three successive post-probe pulses for the different number of acclimatization pulses. Red dashed line with the shaded region shows the mean and SEM of the respective pre-probe amplitudes. Slope and p-value by linear mixed-effects are inset in each plot. (F) Schematic of the experimental protocol for the delayed probe experiments. 3x probe pulses were presented with a variable delay from 1s to 15s after 8x acclimatization pulses. (G) Average response of the backward tuned cells aligned to the onset of the probe pulses. Shaded regions are SEM across N=9 fish. Colors indicate the delay as shown in (F). (H) Amplitude of the response to the first probe pulse does not depend on the delay. ns : $p = 0.98$ by Friedman's test.

4.4.5 Cerebellar granule cells (GCs) encode sensory input but not deviation from expectation

PCs receive excitatory inputs from two distinct synaptic pathways, namely parallel fibers (PFs) from cerebellar granule cells (GCs) and climbing fibers (CFs) from the inferior olive (IO). It is believed that GCs encode sensory context and motor activity whereas the CF pathway carries reinforcing error signals. PF synapses co-active with the error signal are suppressed and those de-correlated with error selectively contribute to PC activity, subsequently affecting behavior. According to this framework of cerebellar function, we would expect GCs to represent an array of sensory tuned responses but not the error in expected optic flow direction.

To identify the input pathway(s) to PCs encoding deviation from the expected direction of optic flow, we performed serial volumetric calcium imaging of the GC population expressing GCaMP6f under the *neurod* promoter (Figures 4.5A,B). A single hemisphere of the cerebellum was densely sampled across 6 imaging planes separated by 10 μ m, yielding a total of 6465 GCs across 8 fish. This accounts for ~27% of all GCs in one hemisphere of the 7-day old larval zebrafish cerebellum. The stimulus protocol consisted of two trials separated by 30s. The first trial was a randomized sequence of stimulus pulses to determine baseline responses of GCs to optic flow. The second trial began with 8 acclimatization pulses of 1cm/s followed by 3 negative probe pulses, then 3 pulses of 1cm/s and ended with an equivalent period of stationary grating (Figure 4.5A).

We then used correlation based hierarchical clustering to identify functional GC response types (Figure 4.5C-G). Clustering was performed independently for each fish using activity

traces from the second trial. The number of clusters per fish was set to 5 with the help of silhouette plots. The clusters were then assigned names based on the relationship of the observed response types to the optic flow stimulus. The same response types were not present across all fish but were largely overlapping (Figure 4.5C-G).

A substantial proportion of cells (43%) were either inactive or sparsely active in a non-stimulus selective manner (Figure 4.5F). 15% of all cells were strongly tuned and an additional 31% were weakly tuned to the forward optic flow stimulus respectively (Figure 4.5C,E). 3% of all cells were activated non-specifically by forward optic flow and exhibited a persistent elevation in calcium activity outlasting the stimulus and/or motor activity (Figure 4.5D). The final cluster consisting of 8% of the sampled GC population included cells that were inhibited by forward optic flow (Figure 4.5G). Importantly, no response type was found tuned to the weak probe stimulus, indicating that the large amplitude responses observed downstream in the PC population were not caused by GC activity.

It is possible that the clustering method failed to identify a sparse subset of GCs tuned to the negative probe stimulus. To address this, we explicitly looked for cells showing responses to the 3 pulses of the negative probe stimuli by cross correlating a short segment of the calcium trace around the probe pulses with the stimulus regressor (Figure 4.5I). By setting a conservative threshold correlation of 0.5, we were able to find 3 ± 3 cells (mean \pm SD) per fish that were tuned to the negative probe stimulus (Figure 4.5I - top, J). Since responses were not trial averaged, lower thresholds than 0.5 picked up correlated imaging noise. Cells identified using this method were not activated by the 1cm/s flow stimulus (Figure 4.5I - bottom). However, they had comparable response amplitude to the negative probe stimulus when presented in random order in the first trial (Figure 4.5K,L), suggesting that this is a sensory representation of the probe stimulus. Moreover, these results strongly suggest that the signal encoding deviation from expectation arrives at the PCs through CF inputs from the IO.

Figure 4.5: Granule cell responses reveal absence of the error signal

(A) Schematic of the experimental protocol. (B) A representative imaging plane (top) and ROIs drawn around GC cell bodies using semi-automated anatomical segmentation (bottom). (C-G) Functional response types identified using correlation based clustering. The cluster label, number of cells (mean \pm SD) and the number of fish in which the cluster was found is inset in each panel. (H) Average motor activity overlaid onto the optic flow stimulus. (I : top) Response of probe responsive cells identified using cross correlation with stimulus regressor. (I : bottom) Response of the same cells shown on top to 1cm/s optic flow. (J) Number of cells identified as probe responsive. (K) Average response of the probe responsive cells to negative probe pulses post acclimatization and when presented at random (baseline). (L) Response amplitude of the probe responsive cells to negative probe when presented randomly compared to the amplitude post acclimatization. ns: $p = 0.11$ by Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Traces shown in C-I, K are mean \pm SEM.

4.4.6 Strong population-wide encoding of stimulus expectation in PCs correlates with lower swim latency

To test whether an expectation of the forward optic flow stimulus might influence swim responses, we looked at the latency with which optomotor responses were generated. In this experiment, fish were presented with a single trial of 100 pulses of optic flow stimuli, consisting of 90 pulses of forward optic flow at 1cm/s and 10 pulses of the negative probe stimulus (Figure S4.6A). The probe stimulus was pseudorandomly interspersed across the experiment. As seen earlier, fish swam consistently in response to forward optic flow and almost no swims were initiated in response to the probe stimulus or during periods of no optic flow (Figure S4.6B). PC calcium activity was imaged simultaneously.

We first sorted cells into forward or backward tuned based on their average calcium responses to each of the stimuli. An average response profile was constructed for each cell by stitching together the average response to forward optic flow and probe (Figure 4.6B). Using regression, we then classified cells as either forward tuned (Figure 4.6B, purple) or backward tuned (Figure 4.6B, black). Since there were 90 pulses of forward optic flow and 10 of probe, we obtained a good classification using a threshold correlation of 0.4 as imaging noise was averaged out effectively. Out of 69 ± 14 cells (mean \pm SD) from 27 fish, 18 ± 5 were backward tuned and 45 ± 11 were forward tuned.

Next, we hypothesized that if swim responses to optic flow were influenced by an expectation based on stimulus history, a stronger expectation could lead to lower latency responses. Previous experiments have shown that an enhanced response to an unexpected probe stimulus encodes the level of deviation from expectation and can be used as a proxy for how strongly fish expect the acclimatization stimulus (Figure 4.4). We therefore looked at both the population averaged amplitude and the probability of occurrence of large calcium transients in response to probe stimuli in backward tuned cells - a high amplitude or probability would imply higher confidence in the expected stimulus pattern and vice versa. Response probability was estimated by counting the occurrence of a large calcium event (> 3 SDs from baseline) during probe pulses. Since probe stimuli were presented infrequently in this experiment, we linearly

interpolated the amplitude and probability to obtain coarse-grained readouts of the expectation of forward optic flow across the 100 stimulus pulses (Figure 4.6A,C). Similarly, latency values were also linearly interpolated and smoothed with a rolling average spanning 10 stimulus pulses. Fish that paused swimming for a continuous sequence of 10 or more pulses were excluded to minimize interpolation artifacts. The 10 pulse long smoothing window matched the average distance between two probe stimuli, thereby yielding a comparably coarse-grained estimate of latency. We then proceeded to compute the Pearson's correlation coefficient between these population-wide readouts of how strongly fish expected forward optic flow and the latency to swim. Swim latency was negatively correlated with both amplitude and response probability (Figure 4.6C,D). These results suggest that fish might incorporate an expectation of optic flow stimulus in planning swim responses to repetitive stimuli.

In the above experiment, if fish indeed initiated swims with lower latency because they expected the forward optic flow stimulus, there should be a neural representation of this expectation when forward optic flow stimuli were presented, whether in PCs or elsewhere. As both forward optic flow and motor activity cause strong PC activation, we decided to look at the calcium activity prior to the onset of the forward optic flow stimulus to exclude sensory and motor contributions to the dF/F signal. For this analysis, we extracted the average pre-flow dF/F for both forward and backward tuned cells and fit a linear mixed-effects model between swim latency and the pre-flow calcium activity. The pre-flow calcium activity in forward tuned cells showed a significant negative correlation with latency (Figure 4.6E). A significant negative correlation could be detected up to ~ 2.5 s before the onset of the stimulus (Figure 4.6H). The correlation was absent when stimulus order was shuffled (Figure 4.6F) and was not present in cells tuned to the backward direction of optic flow (Figure 4.6G). This observation is consistent with the idea that the cells active during forward optic flow are likely the ones involved in the generation of behavioral responses and hence any representation of an expectation of forward optic flow that contributes to behavior is therefore also present in their pre-flow activity and not in the backward tuned cells.

We then performed loose-patch extracellular recordings from PCs in paralyzed fish pre-

sented with repetitive forward optic flow stimuli (Figure 4.6I). Cells that showed strong activation during forward optic flow were selected. All 20 cells that were analyzed showed a strong simple spike (SS) rate increase during forward optic flow stimuli and 15 out of the 20 showed a strong increase in climbing fiber (CF) input rate. In these cells, we saw a significant increase in both SS (Figure 4.6J) and CF input (Figure 4.6K) rate in a 3s window leading up to the onset of forward optic flow. This indicates the possible presence of a predictive component in the activity of PCs, which contributes to the initiation of swim responses to optic flow.

Figure 4.6: Strong population-wide representation of stimulus expectation correlates with lower swim latency

(A) Heatmap of single trial responses of all cells in a representative fish to two instances of the negative probe stimulus. The average motor activity over a window of 10 non-probe stimulus pulses around each of the probes is shown on top. The mean latency to initiate swims and the

population-wide probe response probability are inset in each plot. (B) Regressor-based classification of cells into forward (magenta) and backward (black) tuned using the trial averaged responses to 1cm/s forward optic flow and the negative probe stimulus. Gray traces represent individual fish, N=27. (C) Representative plot from one fish showing latency to swim in response to forward optic flow (pink) along with probe response amplitude (black) and probability (black dashed) for backward tuned cells. (D) Both amplitude and probability are anticorrelated with latency. Green shaded area shows 95% confidence interval for the median estimated by bootstrapping. N=16 fish. (E-G) The pre-flow calcium activity is significantly anticorrelated with latency for the forward tuned cells (E). No correlation is seen when the trial order is shuffled (F) or in backward tuned cells (G). Slope and p-value by linear mixed-effects are inset in each plot. N=27 fish. (H) The pre-flow calcium activity in forward tuned cells is significantly anticorrelated with latency up to 2.5s prior to the onset of the forward optic flow stimulus. (I) Left: Schematic of the experimental preparation used for extracellular loose-patch recordings from PCs. Right : Traces showing the optic flow stimulus, PC recording with simple spikes (SS) and climbing fiber (CF) inputs, fictive motor recording and the processed motor signal used for closed-loop feedback for some fish. Scale : zoomed-out: 2s, zoomed-in: 20ms. (J, K) Both SS (J) and CF input (K) rates show a significant, steady increase prior to the onset of optic flow. *** : $p < 0.001$ by linear mixed-effects. N=20 cells in (J) and N=15 cells in (K).

4.4.7 Unexpected stimuli cause a cerebellum dependent transient elevation in swim latency

Next, we probed for a causal link between cerebellar activity and the expectation dependent component of the optomotor response. If expectation of a stimulus contributed to the generation of lower latency swims, we hypothesized that deviant probe stimuli would perturb behavior and lead to longer latency responses to subsequent presentations of forward optic flow. To quantify this, we looked at a window of 5 optic flow stimulus pulses before and after a probe stimulus (Figure 4.7A,B). The average latency in the window before the probe was considered as the baseline and a fold-change in latency from this baseline was calculated for each of the 10 stimulus pulses in the window around the probe (Figure 4.7B). The probe stimulus caused a significant elevation in latency in response to the next occurrence of the forward optic flow stimulus. The elevated latency returned back to baseline after a single pulse of the forward optic flow stimulus following the probe (Figure 4.7C). This suggests that fish indeed use expectations based on stimulus history to generate optomotor responses.

In order to test a causal role for the cerebellum in this process, we lesioned the cerebellum (Figure 4.7E) in a different group of fish and performed the same experiment as above. Both

lesioned and non-lesioned fish showed similar levels of behavioral responsiveness and the mean latency remained comparable between both groups (Figure 4.7F,G). However, the lesioned fish did not show an elevation in latency after the probe stimulus was presented (Figure 4.7D). The fact that behavior was not perturbed by an unexpected stimulus in lesioned fish indicates that the cerebellum is involved in incorporating expectations based on stimulus history in the generation of swim responses to optic flow, possibly with lower latency.

Figure 4.7: The cerebellum uses a learnt expectation of optic flow stimulus to generate swims with lower latency

(A) Optic flow stimulus protocol used (green) and corresponding motor responses of a representative fish (pink). The positions of the probe stimuli were randomized. (B) Zoomed in view of the highlighted region in (A) Top: showing a probe stimulus ± 5 forward optic flow pulses. Bottom: Calculation of latency modulation around the probe. (C) Average latency modulation

for 10 forward optic flow pulses around the probe stimulus. $N=17$ fish, * : $p = 0.03$, ns : $p = 0.43$ by Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Unexpected probe stimuli cause a transient elevation in latency. (D) Latency modulation around the probe stimulus for cerebellum lesioned fish. $N=11$, ns : $p = 0.79$ by Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Probe stimuli did not cause an elevation in latency in lesioned fish. (E) A single two-photon optical section of the GCaMP6s expressing Purkinje cells before (top) and after (bottom) lesioning. Disintegration and blebbing of cells and neuropil can be seen after the lesioning protocol. Scale bar : $20\mu\text{m}$. (F, G) Both lesioned and non-lesioned fish show similar levels of behavioral responsiveness (F) and respond to optic flow with similar average latency (G). ns : $p > 0.05$ by independent sample t-test.

4.5 Discussion

In this study, we investigated how the brain acquires behavioral timescale internal models of the world to respond more efficiently to predictable stimuli. Using two-photon calcium imaging in head-restrained larval zebrafish in a closed-loop optomotor environment, we identify and characterize a previously unknown expectation based component involved in the optomotor response. Our results show that with experience, fish learn to expect the direction of optic flow stimulus. PCs in the cerebellum are strongly activated by optic flow in a strictly direction selective manner (Figure 4.1). In addition to encoding sensory input, the PC response to optic flow included a component which encoded the degree of unexpectedness of the stimulus, while maintaining direction tuning (Figures 4.2, 4.4). As seen in other systems (Hull, 2020; Keller and Mrcic-Flogel, 2018; Schultz and Dickinson, 2000), we propose that this non-sensory component constitutes an error signal which is critical for maintaining an updated belief of what to expect from the sensory world. Activity in the GC population revealed a variety of sensory tuned responses but not the error signal, indicating that CF inputs from the IO convey error information to PCs (Figure 4.5). A subset of GCs exhibited a persistent stimulus tuned response, which possibly encodes stimulus expectation (Figure 4.5D,G). An error driven learning rule could enable PCs to incorporate appropriate predictive signals from GCs to modulate behavior. The PC population-wide encoding of error, which is a proxy for how strongly fish expect a particular stimulus, correlated negatively with swim latency, suggesting that stimulus expectation might indeed contribute to lowering the latency of swim responses (Figure 4.6A-C). Subsequently, through lesion experiments, we identify a causal role for the cerebellum in latency modulation when unexpected stimuli are encountered (Figure 4.7). In sum, these results point

to a central role for the cerebellum in signaling deviations from expectation and in sculpting motor responses for expected and unexpected stimuli.

4.5.1 Role of the cerebellum in zebrafish optomotor behavior

Previous studies have identified the larval zebrafish pretectum as the primary optic flow processing region involved in the optomotor response (Kramer et al., 2019; Naumann et al., 2016). The cerebellum receives inputs from direction tuned neurons in the pretectum (Kramer et al., 2019) but a direct role for the cerebellum in sensorimotor transformations involved in the optomotor response has not been identified (Kramer et al., 2019; Naumann et al., 2016). Here we show that lesioning the cerebellum does not affect the response latency or swim probability (Figure 4.7F,G). However, unlike control fish, the lesioned fish were not perturbed by an unexpected change in optic flow direction (Figure 4.7C,D), suggesting an inability to incorporate an expectation of optic flow direction into the optomotor response. This shows that the cerebellum does not play a direct role in the generation of the response but is rather involved in biasing behavior based on past experience.

4.5.2 Possible circuit mechanism

The findings presented here give us important insights into the mechanisms employed by the cerebellar circuitry to incorporate an internal model of the sensory world into behavior generation.

4.5.2.1 Dense and persistent sensory representations in GCs

The 7dpf larval zebrafish cerebellum consists of around 6000 GCs which converge onto 300 PCs. Our observation of dense activation of the GC population in response to optic flow stimuli (Figure 4.5C-G) is consistent with recent findings from larval zebrafish (Knogler et al., 2017; Prat et al., 2022) and other species (Giovannucci et al., 2017; Wagner et al., 2017). We also found response profiles in the GC population exhibiting stimulus tuned but persistent elevation in calcium activity (Figure 4.5D,G). One of these response profiles, present in 6 out of 8 fish

(Figure 4.5G), was inhibited strongly by forward optic flow and showed long lasting elevation during periods of no optic flow or probe. It is possible that sensory expectations could be encoded in persistent activity of such a subpopulation. A recent study of GC responses to luminance changes in larval zebrafish also found temporally diverse and persistent activity lasting tens of seconds from stimulus onset (Prat et al., 2022). Depression of GC inputs coincident with error signals from the IO would allow PCs to select response profiles that contribute to error free behavior (Ito, 2000; Narain et al., 2018).

4.5.2.2 Error signals are encoded in CF inputs from the IO

No error representation was present in the GC calcium responses, even though a substantial proportion of them were sampled (Figure 4.5). This strongly suggests that the error signal we see in the PC population, representing the deviation from expected direction of optic flow, is encoded in CF inputs from the IO. Furthermore, it has been observed that large calcium signals recorded from PCs are more likely to be caused by CF driven bursts or calcium spikes than changes in simple spike rates caused by GC activity. It is therefore possible that PC direction tuning (Figure 4.1E) determined by calcium imaging reveals how error signals are tuned for each cell rather than their sensory tuning. Future experiments to determine how error maps onto GC input will provide important insights into cerebellar computation.

How the brain generates error signals has been a long standing question in neuroscience. In order to generate error, there must already be a prediction or an expectation which is compared with ground truth sensory input to determine whether there are mismatches. This error can then be used to update the expectation such that future errors are minimized. In the findings presented here, the error signal is most likely computed by or relayed to IO neurons, which then map onto PCs in the cerebellum. This would indicate that neurons encoding the expected direction of optic flow, either as persistent activity or distributed across the network, are present upstream of the cerebellum.

4.5.2.3 Integration of sensory expectations and error by PCs and their influence on behavior

Individual PCs receive convergent input from a large number of GCs, possibly composed of a variety of different response types. We hypothesize that PCs implement an error driven learning rule that adaptively scales the contribution of GC response types to behavior. Specifically, the inputs to PCs from GCs encoding stimulus expectation that are active during probe get progressively suppressed, thereby contributing less to generating the behavioral response. Multiple observations presented here are consistent with this model. (i) The expectation is updated only when stimuli that are either consistent (repeated forward flow) or inconsistent (deviant probe flow) with the past are experienced (Figure 4.4). Extended periods of no optic flow do not lead to a change in the amplitude of the error response (Figures 4.4G, S4.3), nor does constant optic flow (Figure S4.4). These results point towards an experience gated updating process. (ii) The latency to swim in response to forward optic flow is negatively correlated with the prevalence of error encoding in the PC population (Figure 4.6A-C). Furthermore, the response latency is longer immediately following a probe pulse compared to the pre-probe baseline (Figure 4.7C) but no elevation is seen in cerebellum lesioned fish (Figure 4.7D). This suggests that stimulus expectation might indeed contribute to a lower latency optomotor response.

While the model proposed here provides an algorithmic description of the neural mechanism, it opens up several questions for further investigation. As discussed above, for an error signal to be computed, a comparison between an expectation and ground truth is necessary. It is unclear how the brain acquires this expectation and how it is encoded in neural activity. Examining the activity of IO neurons and the inputs they receive will shed light on this process. Additionally, the role of the cerebellum may not be limited to tuning the influence of expectation on behavior generation. Cerebellar feedback to upstream brain regions could play an important role in acquiring these expectations. Lastly, the output of the cerebellum does not directly cause movements. It remains to be seen how cerebellar output integrates with sensorimotor computations involved in generating the optomotor response.

4.5.3 Ethological relevance of predicting optic flow

Shallow water streams inhabited by larval zebrafish often show repetitive and predictable changes in flow due to water waves or vortex streets shed by objects intercepting laminar flow. Fast and precise reactions to these perturbations caused by flowing water are likely to prevent fish from being washed away from a favorable environmental niche. In our experiments, fish learnt to expect optic flow direction with minimal prior exposure and continuously adapted their internal model with experience. Such an adaptable predictive mechanism functioning on timescales of immediate behavioral requirements is highly relevant in the natural setting. In addition to this homeostatic function, it is possible that fish incorporate predicted environmental perturbations to fine tune other behavioral responses such as escape swims or prey capture maneuvers, such that the motor command generated in these situations compensates for displacement due to expected flow patterns. This study sets up an ideal model to investigate how multiple parallel predictive mechanisms involved in expecting flow induced perturbations and those involved in behaviors such as escape or prey capture, work in concert to ultimately guide appropriate behavioral choices.

4.5.4 Conclusion

Using the accessibility of the larval zebrafish model, we showed that Purkinje cells in the cerebellum can encode expectations of sensory stimuli and report error when the expectation is not met. Such cerebellar computations are incorporated into motor planning so as to generate swims with quick reaction times. These results point to important and conserved functions of the cerebellum in acquiring and updating internal models of the world.

4.6 Supplementary figures

Figure S4.1: Regression-based categorization of PC response tuning

(A) Heat map of calcium activity of all cells imaged in a representative fish in response to a randomized optic flow stimulus sequence. The optic flow stimulus and motor activity of the fish are shown above. Cells are sorted based on the highest regression coefficient as backward tuned (cells 0-37), forward tuned (cells 38-62) or motor tuned (cells 63-68). None of the cells showed strong responses to both forward and backward optic flow. Cells within each group that had a strong individual correlation (Pearson's $r \geq 0.6$) with the respective regressor were then picked. (B, C) The total number of cells in each group (B) and the fraction of all cells that could be classified (C). Gray lines represent individual fish, error bars show SD. (D) Regression coefficients for all cells that could be classified. Cells responding strongly to forward optic flow did not show strong responses to backward optic flow and vice versa (A, D-left panel).

Figure S4.2: Forward tuned cells do not show an enhanced response to positive probe

(A) Left: Calcium response of the forward tuned cells to the positive probe trials (N=7 fish). Right: fold-change in amplitude of the response to positive probe stimuli post acclimatization w.r.t baseline. No increase in probe response amplitude can be seen post acclimatization. (B, C) Calcium response of the forward tuned cells in the negative probe trials (B) and in trials with no probe stimulus after acclimatization (C). No response is seen in forward tuned cells in either of these trials during the probe phase.

Figure S4.3: No enhancement of the response to probe stimulus is seen after extended periods without optic flow

(A, B) The optic flow stimulus in trials with 4 acclimatization pulses (A) and the average response of the backward tuned cells to the first post-probe, aligned to the onset of the probe stimulus (highlighted region in A). Shaded region is SEM across N=8 fish. (C) The optic flow stimulus between two trials showing the 35s interval with no optic flow between the end of the last probe pulse in the previous trial and the first probe pulse in the next trial. (D) The average calcium response of the same backward tuned cells to the first probe stimulus (highlighted region) after the 35s interval with no optic flow. (E) The peak amplitude of the response to probe after 4 acclimatization pulses is significantly greater than the peak amplitude after no optic flow for an equivalent time duration. * : $p = 0.016$ by Wilcoxon signed-rank test. (F) The amplitude post acclimatization is significantly greater than the baseline (zero) whereas the amplitude after the interval with no optic flow is comparable to the baseline amplitude. * : $p = 0.016$, ns : $p = 0.3$ by Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Figure S4.4: Acclimatization to constant optic flow does not lead to enhanced responses to probe

(A) Top: description of the experimental protocol. Middle (green): Stimuli presented in this experiment. A constant 1cm/s forward optic flow stimulus is presented in the acclimatization phase for 32s, 16s, 8s or 4s, corresponding to an equivalent flow-on time duration as the pulsed acclimatization stimuli in Figure 4A. Bottom: Average responses of backward tuned cells to the stimulus shown above. Shaded regions represent SEM across $N=4$ fish. Colors indicate the duration of the acclimatization stimulus. (B) Zoomed in view of the calcium traces shown in (A), aligned to the onset of the first pre-probe stimulus (top) and to the onset of the first post-probe stimulus (bottom). (C, D) No significant scaling of the amplitude of the pre- or post-probe stimuli could be seen. ns : $p = 0.16$ (C) and $p = 0.08$ (D) by Friedman test. (E) Response amplitudes for the first probe stimulus post acclimatization with the pulsed (black, $N=7$ fish) vs constant optic flow (red, $N=4$ fish) of equivalent durations. The probe response amplitudes after pulsed acclimatization are significantly greater than after acclimatization to constant optic flow. * : $p < 0.05$ by Wilcoxon rank-sum test.

Figure S4.5: Repeated presentations of the post-probe stimulus causes a decay of acclimatization induced enhancement of the probe response

(A-E) Decay of the amplitude of the enhanced response to the post-probe stimulus over the three successive post-probe pulses for each of the delays starting from 15s (A) to 1s (E). Slope and p-value by linear mixed-effects are inset in each plot. (F) Average amplitude values from (A-E) overlaid.

Figure S4.6: Experimental protocol to probe whether expectation of a stimulus influences behavioral responses

(A) Schematic of the 100 stimulus pulse long protocol. 10 negative probe stimuli were randomly interspersed amongst 90 swim-inducing 1cm/s forward optic flow stimuli. Zoomed insets show individual probe (left) and forward optic flow (right) stimuli. (B) Forward optic flow pulses of 2s duration reliably evoke swims. Almost no swims were seen in response to the probe stimulus or during the interval between stimuli. $p = 1.01 \times 10^{-13}$ by one-way repeated measures ANOVA, ** : $p = 0.001$ by Tukey's post-hoc test, $N=27$ fish. (C) The mean latency with which swim bouts were initiated from the onset of forward optic flow stimuli.

4.7 References

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Chapter 5

Design and operation of a light-sheet microscope to image brain-wide network dynamics in behaving larval zebrafish

5.1 Introduction

Previous results indicate that neural networks involved in encoding stimulus expectation and error computation are present upstream of the cerebellum. While the inferior olive is the prime candidate region to study error computation, it is unclear where and how stimulus expectation is represented in neuronal population activity. It could either be a low dimensional representation in persistent activity or be distributed across a network of neurons in upstream sensory regions of the brain such as the pretectum. These questions can be effectively addressed by performing experiments similar to those presented in the previous chapter, while simultaneously recording the activity of not only cells within the cerebellum, but the whole brain, at cellular resolution. The larval zebrafish brain is small and transparent and several imaging techniques have been used to record brain activity using calcium sensors at this scale (see below). This chapter details the design, construction and operation of a custom digitally scanned light-sheet microscope to image brain-wide calcium activity at cellular resolution in behaving larval zebrafish. At the end of this chapter, a representative imaging session is discussed as a proof of concept for future experiments. Harshavardan B. N. assisted in building the microscope.

5.1.1 A review of whole-brain imaging methods

At 7dpf, larval zebrafish exhibit a rich repertoire of behaviors (Orger and de Polavieja, 2017) ranging from escape responses to prey capture (Bianco et al., 2011), motor adaptation (Ahrens et al., 2012) and learning (Lin et al., 2020). At this stage of development, fish are transparent and the brain size is small (~100,000 neurons) (Ahrens et al., 2013) making it possible to image calcium activity at cellular resolution from most neurons in the brain within a single recording session in behaving fish. The brain volume fits within a $750 \times 500 \times 300 \mu\text{m}$ FOV

(Ahrens et al., 2013; Kunst et al., 2019; Randlett et al., 2015) (Figure 5.1) and depending on the imaging method used, can be covered simultaneously (Dunn et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2020; Andalman et al., 2019) or by sequentially acquiring smaller FOVs (Ahrens et al., 2012; Bahl and Engert, 2020) to build a whole-brain activity map. Commonly used methods for whole-brain imaging achieve optical sectioning either by selective excitation (two-photon, light-sheet microscopy) or by post-hoc processing (light field microscopy (LFM) and differential illumination focal filtering (DIFF)). The choice of method requires consideration of spatial and temporal resolution, SNR, phototoxicity and the feasibility of implementation (custom vs off the shelf hardware/software).

Figure 5.1: 7dpf larval zebrafish

Left: Freely swimming 7dpf larval zebrafish. Right: A composite image of a head-restrained 7dpf fish with pan-neuronal expression of GCaMP5G (green). A z-projection of GCaMP fluorescence is shown to highlight the brain volume. Scale bar : 100µm.

5.1.2 Two-photon microscopy

Two-photon laser scanning microscopy has been extensively used for functional imaging in conjunction with fluorescent calcium indicators, mainly GCaMP. The spatial resolution of this technique is comparable to confocal microscopy and is determined by the excitation point spread function (PSF). Unlike confocal imaging, since the two-photon excitation is confined to the focal plane, phototoxicity is minimized. Furthermore, the excitation wavelengths used lie within the near-IR spectrum, making it invisible to most animal models used in the field. The excitation light therefore does not cause interference to the behavior of the animal. The

major drawback of this method is that imaging rates are limited due to point scanning and faster scan rates impact SNR. Therefore, studies in which two-photon whole-brain imaging of larval zebrafish has been carried out have performed sequential scans over multiple FOVs (Ahrens et al., 2012; Bahl and Engert, 2020), while repeating a behavior protocol.

Recent advances have been made to greatly improve two-photon imaging rates. SLAP microscopy (Kazemipour et al., 2019) achieves kilohertz rates using post-hoc computational unmixing of simultaneously acquired overlapping lines. Light beads microscopy (Demas et al., 2021) uses 30 temporally multiplexed excitation beams focused at different depths to achieve simultaneous volumetric imaging at single frame acquisition rates. These techniques have been recently developed and require complex set-ups. Their accessibility to the wider community remains to be seen.

5.1.3 Light-sheet microscopy

Light-sheet microscopy involves projecting a sheet of excitation light through the brain along a plane orthogonal to the detection arm of the microscope. After capturing an image, a new plane is illuminated by the sheet. The focal plane of the detection arm is moved correspondingly and the next image is captured. This cycle is repeated to achieve volumetric imaging. The sheet is either created by focusing a laser beam into a sheet with a cylindrical lens or by rapidly scanning an extremely narrow (< 1 cell diameter) beam of light into a sheet (Keller et al., 2015). Since the rate at which each plane is captured is limited by the exposure time of the camera used and the re-focusing time in case of volumetric imaging, sufficiently high speeds can easily be obtained for whole-brain volumetric imaging of calcium activity or very fast, single plane imaging of voltage sensors in narrow FOVs. As much longer exposure times per pixel can be used when compared to two-photon imaging, the excitation intensity can be greatly reduced while achieving substantially higher SNR. This makes light-sheet imaging an ideal method for simultaneous (w.r.t. calcium sensor dynamics) whole-brain volumetric imaging in 7dpf larval zebrafish.

There are however several practical limitations to light-sheet microscopy. Conventional

sheet forming techniques with a cylindrical lens or a scanned narrow beam result in a non-uniform sheet with a waist centered around the focal plane of the excitation objective. Although cellular resolution can be obtained across the volume of the whole larval zebrafish brain, it is insufficient to image finer structural detail. The sheet also suffers substantially from scattering as it propagates through tissue and occlusions such as blood vessels cast shadows along the axis of excitation. Methods have been developed to overcome these limitations (Taylor et al., 2018). Lastly, most examples of light-sheet microscopy use one-photon excitation. Visible wavelength excitation light can interfere with the behavior of the animal. Larval zebrafish studies typically blank the laser around the eye of the fish using a physical mask placed in the excitation arm or by restricting the scanning to avoid illuminating the eyes with the sheet. In both cases, to excite brain tissue occluded by the eyes of the fish, a second sheet is required. Two-photon light-sheet microscopy has been used to image calcium activity in larval zebrafish and could potentially be a viable alternative to overcome these limitations (Wolf et al., 2015).

5.1.4 Whole-brain imaging in unrestrained fish

Complex behaviors such as hunting and goal directed navigation are difficult to study in head-restrained fish. Although virtual reality has been used to study these in restrained fish (Dunn et al., 2016), behavior in the virtual world is not the same as in the real world. A key point of difference is that restrained fish show very low rates of spontaneous swimming, whereas constant swimming at ~ 1 -1.5Hz is seen when unrestrained. Paralyzed fish placed in a closed-loop environment exhibit much higher rates of spontaneous swimming but differences in behavior still exist (Dunn et al., 2016). While these differences may not sufficiently impact the behavior being studied, restraining the fish is not always feasible (Kim et al., 2017).

To overcome this limitation, LFM (Cong et al., 2017) and DIFF (Kim et al., 2017) microscopy have been used to image calcium activity at cellular resolution in freely moving fish. In both these studies, the fish position was tracked in real time and the microscope stage was moved to keep the brain within the FOV of the imaging objective. Of the two imaging methods, LFM offers true simultaneous volumetric imaging and has been used previously to image whole-brain activity in restrained larval zebrafish (Andalman et al., 2019). The true simultane-

ous readout of activity from LFM can be used to more accurately track information flow across distant brain regions.

5.1.5 Analysis and interpretation of brain-wide activity

Whole-brain imaging datasets are large and can be in the range of 1TB or more, per hour, per fish (Freeman et al., 2014). The initial step of extracting fluorescence time-series data for individual voxels or ROIs takes many days on a desktop workstation but can be made substantially more efficient using distributed computing. Freeman et al. (2014), have created a user friendly, open-source solution to this problem. In addition to providing a solution for voxel based analysis of large scale light-sheet or two-photon imaging data, their python package also implements regression and PCA based analysis of neural activity.

Recording the activity of more neurons does not necessarily lead to a deeper understanding of brain function. Whole-brain imaging in fish has most effectively been used as a tool to test or add detail to pre-existing hypotheses or theoretical frameworks with the help of targeted manipulation and informative experiment design (Bahl and Engert, 2020; Mu et al., 2019). Apart from targeted manipulations of circuit function, it has often proven useful to combine brain activity maps with anatomical information (Randlett et al., 2015; Kunst et al., 2019; Kramer et al., 2019) and/or cell-type identity (Lovett-Barron et al., 2020), for example neurotransmitter type, when evaluating possible circuit mechanisms contributing to behavior.

5.2 Design and construction of a custom digitally scanned light-sheet microscope

This section details the design, construction and operation of a custom digitally scanned light-sheet microscope to image whole-brain calcium activity using GCaMP or to perform single plane, narrow FOV imaging of voltage indicators.

5.2.1 Optical layout

The optical layout of the microscope is similar to those described by Fahrbach et al. (2013) and Taylor et al. (2018). An excitation arm built horizontally on an optical table projects a

digitally scanned sheet of excitation light into the sample. A vertical detection arm images fluorescence emission from the volume illuminated by the sheet within the FOV of the detection objective, onto an sCMOS sensor. Fast scanning to form the sheet from a narrow beam of light and shifting the vertical position of the sheet within the sample are achieved using a pair of galvanometer mirrors. The focal plane of the detection arm is adjusted to be coincident with the plane of the sheet with the help of an electrically tunable lens (ETL). Subsequent ray diagrams show an x-z projection and the fast y-scan axis forming the sheet is not shown to maintain clarity. The following sections go into the design of the microscope in detail. Table 5.1 contains a list of optical components used.

Figure 5.2: Optical layout of the light-sheet microscope

The excitation light path is shown in blue and the detection path is shown in green. The schematic shown is an x-z projection and the sheet forming y-scan axis is perpendicular to the plane of the drawing.

Component	Part number
Excitation path	
Laser	488nm 20mW, Coherent Sapphire LP
Beam expander	BE02-05-A, Thorlabs
Mirrors	BB1-E02, Thorlabs
Excitation filter	ZET488/10x, Chroma
Scan mirrors	GVSM002-EC/M, Thorlabs
Scan lens	AC508-080-A-ML, Thorlabs
Tube lens	AC508-150-A-ML, Thorlabs
Objective	XLFLUOR4X/340, Olympus
Detection path	
Objective	XLUMPLFLN20XW, Olympus
Emission filter	ET525/50m, Chroma
Tube lens	AC508-150-A-ML, Thorlabs
Relay lenses	AC508-080-AB-ML, Thorlabs
Offset lens	Either LC1315-A-ML or LC1093-A-ML, Thorlabs, or none
ETL	EL-10-30-C, Optotune
sCMOS camera	Orca-Flash4.0 V2, Hamamatsu

Table 5.1: Light-sheet microscope parts list of optical elements

Excitation arm:

1: Y, Z galvos, 2: tube lens, 3: scan lens, 4: objective, 5: sample chamber

Detection arm:

6: objective, 7: tube lens, 8: relay lens #1, 9: ETL with offset lens,
10: relay lens #2, 11: sCMOS camera

Figure 5.3: Photograph of the light-sheet microscope

5.2.1.1 Formation of the light-sheet

The spatial resolution of the microscope in the z dimension is determined by the thickness of the excitation light-sheet. The sheet is formed by focusing a narrow laser beam using a low NA, long working distance objective lens (Olympus 4X 0.28NA). The diameter of the laser beam is set to be much smaller than the back aperture of the excitation objective. This results in a narrow focused beam, which is scanned along the y-axis to generate a sheet of excitation light. The thickness of the waist of the narrow excitation beam and the distance along the x-axis with cellular resolution beam thickness can be controlled by adjusting the input beam diameter upstream of the excitation objective. The waist thickness and the usable length along the x-axis can be determined by calculating the excitation beam geometry, assuming a Gaussian cross-section (Figure 5.4) (<https://openspim.org>). Simulations were performed with the equations discussed below to determine the required input beam diameter and select the focal lengths of the scan and tube lenses. The radius of the waist of the Gaussian beam is given by the following equation:

$$w_0 = \frac{n \times \lambda}{\pi \times NA_{eff}} \quad (5.1)$$

Where w_0 is the half-width of the waist of the beam where the intensity drops to $1/e^2$ of the maximum value, n is the refractive index of the medium, λ is the wavelength of light and NA_{eff} is the effective numerical aperture of the focusing lens. To determine the z-resolution of light-sheet microscopes, the full width at half maximum intensity (FWHM) is used as a more relevant measure than w_0 (Ahrens et al., 2013). The FWHM is estimated as $\ln(2) \times w_0$. The usable sheet length along the x-axis can be estimated using the Rayleigh length, z_r (equation 5.2), which is the distance from the waist at which the peak intensity drops to half and $w = \sqrt{2} \times w_0$. The sheet length within this window on either side of the waist is therefore $2 \times z_r$.

$$z_r = \frac{\pi \times w_0^2}{\lambda} \quad (5.2)$$

Reducing the input beam diameter to be smaller than the back aperture of the excitation objective decreases the effective NA and results in a larger waist thickness, while increasing the usable sheet length. A balance between z_r and w_0 must be achieved to maximize the FOV while maintaining cellular resolution. Once the effective NA is determined from equations 5.1 and 5.2, the input beam diameter can be calculated using the following method:

The largest diameter parallel beam of light which can enter the back aperture of the excitation objective (d_{pupil}) is given by equation 5.3. NA_{obj} and f_{obj} are the numerical aperture and the focal length of the excitation objective respectively.

$$d_{pupil} = 2 \times NA_{obj} \times f_{obj} \quad (5.3)$$

Using the small angle approximation of $\sin\theta \approx \theta$, the input beam diameter required for obtaining the desired NA_{eff} can be calculated using the following equation:

$$d_{beam} \approx \frac{NA_{eff}}{NA_{obj}} \times d_{pupil} \quad (5.4)$$

Figure 5.4: Gaussian beam profile

Zoomed-in view of the waist of the focused Gaussian beam with parameters annotated. Image

redrawn based on https://openspim.org/SPIM_Optics_101_Theoretical_basics.

Calculations were performed with $n = 1.33$, $NA_{obj} = 0.28$ and $\lambda = 488nm$. Figure 5.5A shows simulated values for w_0 and z_r for a range of input beam diameters. A usable range for input beam diameter was chosen and the focal lengths of the scan and tube lenses were set as 80mm and 150mm respectively, resulting in a magnification ratio of 1.875. Figure 5.5B shows the estimated FWHM of the sheet as a function of distance from its waist for an input diameter of 3mm, calculated using the following equation:

$$w(z) = w_0 \times \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{z}{z_r}\right)^2} \quad (5.5)$$

Figure 5.5: Intensity profile of the excitation light-sheet

(A) Simulated waist thickness and Rayleigh length of the light-sheet as a function of input beam diameter when focused by the Olympus 4x 0.28NA objective lens. (B) Simulated sheet thickness as a function of distance from the waist for a 3mm input beam. (C) Image of the sheet width obtained by illuminating a chamber filled with fluorescent dye. Scale bar : 100 μm . (D) FWHM of the sheet as a function of distance from the waist, measured by fitting gaussian profiles along its cross-section. Red lines in (B) and (C) indicate average cell size.

In practice, the sheet thickness and divergence can be fine tuned by changing the beam diameter by adjusting the variable beam expander in the light path (Figure 5.2). The usable sheet length along the y-axis is limited only by the FOV of the scan configuration and far exceeds the length of the larval zebrafish brain. Therefore, by orienting the fish such that its body is along the y-axis, a whole-brain cellular resolution FOV can be obtained, provided the beam thickness remains less than cell size for a distance \geq brain width along the x-axis.

5.2.1.2 Detecting fluorescence emission

Fluorescence emission was imaged using a high NA, long working distance objective lens (Olympus XLUMPLFLN20XW), onto the sensor of a Hamamatsu Orca-Flash4.0 V2 sCMOS camera. As the sheet scanned the sample in the z-axis, the focal plane of the detection arm was remotely changed to match the new sheet plane using an ETL (Optotune 10-30-C). Since both the z-galvo and ETL exhibit very good input-output linearity, a simple mapping of the linear range of the ETL onto the range of the z-galvo was used to make the sheet plane and the focal plane of the detection arm collinear. This protocol is described in detail in a separate section below. Due to the narrow aperture of the ETL, it is placed at the conjugate plane of the back aperture of the objective, created in between two relay lenses placed in a 4f configuration as shown in Figure 5.2. The optical configuration and design considerations are described in detail in Fahrbach et al. (2013). In brief, the relay lens focal length must be chosen such that the size of the image of the back aperture of the objective is narrower than the aperture of the ETL. In order for the magnification of the detection system to be independent of focal length of the ETL, it must be placed precisely at the conjugate plane of the objective back aperture. Lastly, the x-y position of the ETL needs to be adjusted with a precision translation mount to be perfectly centered around the optical axis to avoid x-y shifts in the image as the focal length of the ETL is changed.

The range of focus offered by the ETL is 200 μ m, whereas the scan range of the z-galvo is several times larger. The detection arm of the microscope was built on a heavy-duty 2D micrometer stage (Holmarc) on a vertical optical rail (Thorlabs). The x-y and z position of the detection arm was manually adjusted using the micrometer stage and the optical rail re-

spectively such that the focal range of the ETL fell within the scan range of the z-galvo. The collinearity calibration was then performed in software by mapping the range of the ETL onto the range of the z-galvo.

5.2.1.3 Sample positioning

The fish is mounted in a drop of low melting point agarose placed in the center of a 3D printed chamber. Removing as much agarose as possible from the dorsal side of the head is essential to prevent scattering of the sheet. The chamber is then filled with filtered aquarium water and locked into place on an x-y-z translation stage for fine positioning. Two of the four walls of the chamber are made of glass coverslips to facilitate illumination by the light-sheet. The bottom of the chamber is made of a clear acrylic sheet to facilitate visual stimulus presentation and behavior monitoring. A closed-loop behavior setup (Methods chapter) was built beneath the sample chamber and mounted on the same translation stage. The fish brain is brought within the FOV of the imaging camera using wide-field illumination from the visual stimulus projector, with the emission filter removed.

Figure 5.6: 3D printed sample chamber with glass coverslip walls

Left: schematic of the sample chamber drawn to scale. 1: Excitation objective. 2: 3D printed chamber. 3: A 2D transverse section of the narrow focused beam of excitation light used to form the sheet. 4: Larval zebrafish restrained in agarose (not to scale). 5: 22×40 glass coverslip wall. 6: Clear acrylic bottom. Right: photograph of the chamber with green fluorescent dye excited by a narrow 488nm beam of light.

5.2.2 Functional layout

Scanning and acquisition from the microscope was controlled using a custom hardware interface and μ Manager. All of the microscope hardware, apart from the sCMOS camera interfaced with a python GUI through a purpose built control circuit. This control circuit generated scan commands, set ETL focus and triggered camera acquisition. μ Manager was used to configure exposure settings and acquire frames from the camera when triggered by the control circuit, or in free-running mode when calibrating alignment or positioning the sample.

5.2.2.1 Control structure

Scan parameters set using the python GUI are sent using a serial communication protocol to a Teensy 3.6 microcontroller part of the control circuit. The Teensy generates the y, z and ETL scan waveforms using 3 independent analog output channels. In sync with scanning, corresponding frame triggers are sent to the sCMOS camera. The camera captures a single frame per trigger with the exposure time equal to the time taken for one scan of the sheet in the y-axis. The frame rate of acquisition of multiple images is therefore determined by the interval between successive frame triggers, as long as the exposure plus readout time of the camera is shorter than this interval. Camera acquisition can either be configured in global shutter mode or in rolling shutter mode. In the rolling shutter mode, the exposure of each row of pixels on the camera sensor is timed to be in sync with the movement of the excitation beam as it sweeps across the sensor. All camera parameters are set using μ Manager through the default interface for Hamamatsu cameras. The control circuit can be set to an external trigger mode where the acquisition of frames or 3D volumes for a pre-determined length of time is initiated by a single start trigger from an external source, such as the behavior experiment control software.

5.2.2.2 Python GUI and the control circuit

The primary function of the GUI and the control circuit is to generate the voltage commands shown in Figure 5.8. The GUI offers a convenient interface to change acquisition parameters on the fly. The y and z galvos move bidirectionally and their angular position is linearly dependent

Figure 5.7: Control structure of the light-sheet microscope

on the amplitude of a bidirectional voltage signal (Figure 5.8). Similarly, the ETL focal length is linearly dependent on a unidirectional, positive voltage signal (Figure 5.8). The exposure time, FOV and frame rate of acquisition are controlled by appropriately varying these control signals and the associated frame triggers. For example, the exposure time depends on the slope of the y scan waveform and y-FOV depends on the y scan amplitude. z-galvo and ETL positions are varied in steps at the end of each frame in case volumetric imaging is being performed. They remain stationary across frames when in single plane mode.

Apart from controlling scanning and acquisition, this interface enables the user to set analog voltage ranges to match new hardware being used and to co-align the sheet plane with the ETL plane using a 3-point calibration protocol. User settings and calibration are saved in a CSV file and can be loaded as required. This allows fast implementation of multiple pre-set acquisition protocols. The GUI and the firmware on the Teensy together implement a modular finite-state machine (Figure 5.10). This enables new functionality, such as custom scan modes, to be added with minimal programming experience. The arrows in Figure 5.10 indicate possible transitions and the blocks represent states. The start trigger is internally generated when focus mode is selected.

Figure 5.8: Control signals for scanning and acquisition

Figure 5.9: Screenshot of the python GUI

Figure 5.10: Finite-state machine implemented by the python GUI and teensy firmware

5.2.2.3 Co-aligning the excitation and detection arms

As described in the above sections, the ETL focal plane must be co-aligned with the excitation sheet plane in order to form a sharp focused image of the sheet plane on the camera sensor. Once the manual alignment described above has been performed, the ETL range will lie completely within the scan range of the z-galvo. At this stage, the fine calibration protocol implemented in software must be carried out. The calibration protocol requires the excitation beam to be visualized by the camera. This is achieved by filling the sample chamber with a dilute fluorescent dye to make the path of the beam visible. Next, the Teensy is set to calibration mode and the 'Calibrate' button on the GUI is pressed to open the calibration interface.

Calibration is performed using the following protocol:

1. Set ETL voltage to maximum.
2. Adjust z-galvo command voltage to bring the beam into focus.
3. Press the 'Set Max Z' button to save this value.

4. Set ETL voltage to minimum.
5. Adjust z-galvo command voltage to bring the beam into focus.
6. Press the 'Set Min Z' button to save this value.
7. Press the 'Get Zero' button to obtain the mid-point of this range.
8. Check whether the beam is in focus with both ETL and z-galvo at their respective mid-points.
9. Iterate through steps 1-8 if required until both focal planes are coincident.
10. If step 9 fails, confirm whether the ETL is used within its linear command voltage range.
11. Save the calibration to the configuration file.
12. Close the calibration window and re-load the newly saved configuration in the main GUI.
13. Exit calibration mode.

5.2.2.4 Control circuit design

The control circuit was built around a Teensy 3.6 microcontroller. Accessory circuits were added to obtain 3 independent analog output channels with the necessary voltage range to control the y, z galvos and the ETL. The accessory circuits for generating the y and z scan commands were connected to the native analog output channels on the Teensy, driven by the onboard DAC. These circuits performed analog scaling operations to linearly transform the unidirectional 0-3.3V range of the Teensy DAC to a bidirectional -10 to +10V output range to connect to the scan mirror driver boards (Duke, 2013). In order to drive the ETL, a third analog output channel was added using an external I2C-DAC. The 0-3.3V output of the I2C DAC chip was scaled linearly to 0-10V and connected to the ETL driver. All of the scaling circuits were built using strategically placed variable resistors for cross-calibration against a precision National Instruments multi-function data acquisition card. The scaling circuits were manually calibrated to >99% accuracy w.r.t the National Instruments DAQ. Other digital input/output

channels were directly connected to the respective pins on the Teensy. The schematic of the control circuit board is shown below. Signal lines with the same annotation are connected to each other. The schematic is presented as a reference for future users and had to be split into two parts due to size constraints (Figures 5.12 and 5.13). An annotated model of the printed circuit board is shown below indicating the connections to be made to various devices (Figure 5.11).

Connections shown in grey are optional

- | | |
|---|----------------------------|
| 1 : USB connection with the python GUI | 10 : Camera ready input |
| 2 : +-15V Bipolar, low noise power supply | 11 : Abort scan |
| 3 : Z-scan command voltage | 12 : 3.3V reference out |
| 4 : Y-scan command voltage | 13 : Strobe output laser 1 |
| 5 : ETL command voltage | 14 : Strobe output laser 2 |
| 6 : Optional I2C interface | 15 : Strobe output laser 3 |
| 7 : External trigger input | 16 : Shutter |
| 8 : Frame trigger output to camera | 17 : Digital input/output |
| 9 : Frame trigger input from camera | 18 : Digital input/output |

Figure 5.11: Hardware connections to the control circuit

Figure 5.12: Schematic of the control board part 1

Figure 5.13: Schematic of the control board part 2

Component	Value/Name
Integrated Circuits (ICs)	
U1	Teensy 3.6 microcontroller
U2-4	OP07 ultralow offset opamp
U5	MCP4725 I2C DAC
Resistors	
R pulldown	4.7k Ω
R pullup	4.7k Ω
RLED1,2	4.7k Ω
RG1,3	3.3k Ω
RG2,4,5	2.2k Ω
RISO1-3	82 Ω
RFB1-3	6.8k Ω
TRIM1-5	500 Ω variable resistor
Capacitors	
C1-2	47 μ F
CLOAD1-3	20nF, optional
CCOMP1-2	150pF, optional
C3-9	0.22 μ F
CDAC1	0.22 μ F

Table 5.2: List of components used in the control circuit

5.3 Imaging brain-wide activity at cellular resolution

Imaging sessions were carried out to test whether the microscope was capable of capturing whole-brain calcium activity at cellular resolution for extended periods of time. First, a single plane with an x-y FOV of $798 \times 798 \mu\text{m}$ was acquired (Figure 5.14). Single cells could be clearly resolved with this FOV and can be seen as rings of bright cytoplasmic GCaMP5G expression surrounding darker nuclei in Figure 5.14. Stripe and shadow artifacts caused by obstruction of the sheet by tissue such as blood vessels can also be seen. These artifacts are expected in light-sheet microscopy and their influence on the detected calcium signal is typically within acceptable limits (Ahrens et al., 2013; Taylor et al., 2018).

Next, an example dataset was acquired in which 24 planes separated by $9.4 \mu\text{m}$ were acquired simultaneously at 1.02Hz for a duration of 12.7 minutes. Figure 5.15 shows orthogonal projections of a single z-cross section acquired during this imaging session. Figure 5.16 shows a montage of all 24 frames acquired. Individual images have been scaled down by a factor of 5 to make this montage. Single cells are therefore not visible at this resolution.

Calcium traces were extracted from a representative imaging plane $142 \mu\text{m}$ below the dorsal surface of the brain (Figure 5.17). Voxel-wise analysis was performed similar to Ahrens et al. (2013). The image was downsampled to soma-sized voxels and dF/F was calculated for each voxel. Cross-correlation based hierarchical agglomerative clustering was performed to group voxels based on consistencies in fluctuations of dF/F over time. Several correlated ensembles could be observed across the imaging plane (Figure 5.17B). Traces from a representative ensemble and the spatial localization of highly correlated voxels contained within it are shown in Figure 5.17C and D respectively.

5.4 Summary

This chapter describes in detail the design, construction and operation of a custom digitally scanned light-sheet microscope to perform brain-wide cellular resolution calcium imaging in behaving larval zebrafish. A whole-brain imaging dataset was acquired and calcium events were detected in a subset of neurons as a proof of concept for future experiments. Data pre-

sented from preliminary imaging experiments demonstrates that the microscope can be used for stable brain-wide activity imaging over experimentally relevant timescales.

Figure 5.14: A representative $798 \times 798 \mu\text{m}$ single plane FOV demonstrating sub-cellular resolution

Top: a representative imaging plane from a HuC:GCaMP5G transgenic larval zebrafish. Bottom: zoomed-in $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ ROIs showing single cells clearly resolved in the optic tectum (left) and hindbrain (right). The ROIs are indicated in the image above by dashed outlines.

Figure 5.15: Orthogonal projections of a $798 \times 798 \times 225 \mu\text{m}$ brain volume. (left: xy projection, right: yz projection)

Figure 5.16: Montage of the 24-plane, $798 \times 798 \times 225 \mu\text{m}$ brain volume acquired simultaneously at 1.02Hz

Figure 5.17: Calcium traces extracted from ROIs detected in a representative imaging plane

A) A representative imaging plane selected for calcium trace extraction from a simultaneously acquired brain volume. B) Cross-correlation matrix of all voxels within the spatial extent of the brain in the representative z-plane, ordered by cluster. C) Example heat-map of dF/F from 509 individual voxels part of a representative cluster. The blue trace shows the average dF/F for all voxels in the cluster. D) Spatial distribution of 127 highly correlated voxels shown in C.

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Chapter 6

Concluding remarks

6.1 Summary of work presented

The initial stages of the work done for this thesis resulted in the design and construction of a closed-loop virtual environment for head-restrained larval zebrafish. This setup was integrated with a custom two-photon microscope to carry out all of the experiments involving population activity imaging in behaving fish. Several other tools and analysis techniques were set up as part of this work and have been described in detail in the methods chapter, along with instructions for future users.

The first project presents results from closed-loop gain adaptation experiments. These results show that fish adapt their motor output when the outcome of a motor command does not match an internally generated expectation. Adaptation proceeds in parallel through both immediate compensation of ongoing movements and a slow update of an internal model of how motor commands map onto real world consequences. While these results largely agree with what has already been shown by previous studies, several open questions remain and are discussed along with the results. In brief, there is evidence for the involvement of the cerebellum in gain adaptation but whether it implements an error feedback loop similar to mammalian systems remains to be investigated.

The next part of the thesis introduces a novel behavioral paradigm to study how behavioral timescale internal models are learnt and used by the brain. These results uncover an experience dependent predictive component involved in the optomotor response in larval zebrafish. In this behavioral paradigm, fish learn to expect optic flow direction by integrating probability of occurrence over minute-timescales and generate lower latency swim responses to predictable stimuli. Analysis of simultaneously obtained neuronal population activity suggests that Purkinje cells in the cerebellum combine error input from the inferior olive and predictions from granule cells to selectively incorporate valid predictions to generate lower latency swim re-

sponses. In sum, these results point to a central role for the cerebellum in incorporating event probabilities learnt with experience to guide behaviors.

6.2 Significance and future directions

How the brain learns to predict is an ongoing, heavily researched topic in the field. The work presented here shows for the first time that the cerebellum in larval zebrafish implements error feedback loops to learn behavioral timescale internal models of the world. In these experiments, fish use an internally generated expectation of the stimulus pattern in their environment to generate error signals to guide learning. An expectation is present immediately and evolves in real-time to predict the probability of a salient stimulus in the environment. This innate ability of the brain to generate relevant predictions to guide behavior and a role for the cerebellum suggests that it is a highly conserved and fundamental aspect of brain function. The tractability of the zebrafish model system can be exploited to take these findings forward to determine how the brain, and specifically the cerebellar circuit, learns to predict relevant stimuli using error feedback loops.

Appendix - 1

Setup for behavior-triggered optogenetic stimulation

This section describes the design and operation of an experimental setup to perform closed-loop optogenetics in paralyzed larval zebrafish during fictive optomotor behavior. The setup was built as part of a collaboration with Vandana Agarwal to study the effect of population level synchrony of Purkinje cell activity on eurydendroid cell firing and its role in motor control. Representative recordings shown here are from experiments performed by Vandana.

3 Design of the stimulation setup

A custom experimental setup was put together to perform multi-trial optogenetic activation experiments synchronized with patch-clamp recordings from single neurons in the cerebellum. Using an LCD screen connected to the same setup, optic flow stimuli are presented to evoke swimming and depending on the experiment, fictive motor recordings may be used to trigger optogenetic stimulation in closed-loop.

Figure A1.1: Schematic of the experimental setup

The setup was built around an Olympus BX61WI microscope with the same hardware for electrophysiology as described in the methods chapter (section 2.11). The core of the setup consists of a purpose built control circuit, which can be programmed through a user interface written in Python (Figure A1.3). The circuit consists of analog scaling circuitry to transform the bidirectional $\pm 14\text{V}$ range of the electrophysiology amplifier to a unidirectional 0-3V range, which is sampled at 50kHz on a Teensy 3.2 microcontroller. The scaling operation is performed using 3 opamps (Figure A1.3). The input stage of the circuit scales down the $\pm 14\text{V}$ signal to $\pm 3\text{V}$ in an inverting configuration. Next, the second and third opamps with the help of diodes D1 and D2, generate the absolute value of the input voltage at the output (Jones and Stitt, 1997).

The axon instruments hardware used to record electrophysiology data generated a TTL trigger signal at the start of each sweep (trial). This trigger signal initiated a stimulation trial in the Teensy, which then transmits a soft trigger through the serial port to the Python software for controlling visual stimulus delivery. Once the sweep has begun, the Teensy generates ON/OFF signals to control the stimulation LED. The stimulation LED can either be continuously ON during a specified window, pulsed at a user defined frequency or be either continuous or pulsed only when motor events occur. In parallel, optic flow stimuli are generated using PsychoPy (Peirce et al., 2019) by the Python software.

Multi-trial experiments are defined using a built-in protocol editor in the Python GUI. Protocols are saved in JSON format and are loaded onto the GUI before starting an experiment. Once triggered, the GUI uses its internal representation of the state of the experiment to update sweep parameters on the Teensy via serial communication. Updating parameters is done at the end of each sweep so as to not interrupt the timing of stimulation.

Figure A1.2: Representative recording showing control signals generated for closed-loop optogenetic stimulation

Left: A single sweep of an experimental protocol. Motor events are detected online and are used to trigger pulsed optogenetic stimulation at a pre-defined frequency of 33Hz. Right: Zoomed in view of a single motor bout highlighted in the left panel.

Figure A1.3: Schematic of the control circuit board

Parts: U1: TL074 quad opamp, U2: Teensy 3.2 microcontroller, Resistors: R1: 9.8KΩ, R2: 2.2KΩ, R3-5: 10KΩ, Capacitors: C1,4,5: 0.22μF, C2: 10nF, C3: 15pF, Diodes: D1,2: 1N4148 signal diodes, D3,4: 4.7V zener diodes.

4 Instructions for use

1. Connect the control circuit to the electrophysiology hardware and the stimulation LED. Connections to be made are shown below in Figure A1.4. Check the pin assignments in the Teensy firmware to make sure it matches with the Figure. If not, connect according to the version of the firmware currently in use. Serial port name in the GUI should match the port that the Teensy is plugged into.

Figure A1.4: Annotated model of the control circuit

2. Connect the real-time motor detection output, optogenetics trigger and stimulus period output on the control circuit to external analog input channels on the electrophysiology digitizer. Record these signals along with the electrophysiology data.
3. Create and save a protocol for the stimulation experiment using the protocol editor tool in the Python GUI. A separate protocol must be created using Clampex software for recording the same number of sweeps as there are trials in the stimulation protocol. A TTL trigger output must be configured at the beginning of each sweep in the Clampex protocol, which will be used to trigger the Teensy to execute each trial.

4. Load the JSON file containing the protocol on the GUI using the 'Load' button in the 'Experiment Configuration' section. Check the 'use' box to use the loaded protocol file.
5. Set the threshold for real-time motor event detection by adjusting the slider between 0-4095, corresponding to 0-3.3V. Use an oscilloscope to monitor the output voltage on jumper-4 in Figure A1.5, to determine the threshold voltage for motor output detection. Alternatively, the threshold can also be calculated easily from the recordings visualized on the screen in Clampex.
6. In addition to setting the threshold, a window for rolling averaging of the fictive motor signal (default = 3) and the maximum within-bout spike interval (default = 75ms) may be adjusted if required.
7. Set the optic flow stimulus parameters. Pixel size, stimulus window size and display number must be set correctly in the 'Visual Stimulus' section.
8. Next, the parameters defining the optic flow stimulus must be set. If a protocol file is being used, optic flow velocity and duration need not be set.
9. If a protocol file is not being used, a stimulation protocol can be defined using the 'Optogenetic Stimulation' section. A document containing a description of the parameters in this section is present in the same directory as the Python file and can be opened using the 'Protocol Help' button.
10. Update parameters on the Teensy by pressing the 'Update Parameters' button. Press the 'Start' button, the system will now execute trials sequentially when triggered by individual sweeps in Clampex.
11. Run the Clampex protocol. The experiment will be carried out to completion.

Figure A1.5: Screenshot of the user interface software

5 References

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